

Editorial

Dear Reader,

This year's inaugural editorial is penned against a backdrop of a significant milestone—the Highland Institute's 10th anniversary on 10th June. In this past decade, the institute has matured into a reputable, independent research centre, and as a journal under its wing, we are honoured to have participated in this critical decade of growth and maturity.

The institute and the journal perceive research collaboration as a cherished asset in our contemporary era. Navigating the tumultuous transformations underway in Highland Asia - economic, political, social, and indeed climactic - necessitates a certain tenacity for such fundamentals as equitable partnership, quality data, unbiased analysis, and resistance to censorship. Indispensable to truly maintaining this ethos is nurturing a spirit of openness, while maintaining independence from any kind of interference. In a world where the allure of social prestige, profit and the erosion of intellectualism can undermine even the most respected scholarly organisations we take pride in the Highland Institute's and Highlander Journal's steadfast commitment to these values.

This tenth year serves not merely as an anniversary but as a pivotal juncture for introspection and future planning. It presents an opportunity for both the journal and the institute to evaluate the resilience of our shared philosophy and ensure its continued relevance in the upcoming decade. Before delving into the contents of this issue, I'd like to shed light on three initiatives currently spearheaded by the Highland Institute.

MyClimate: Climate Actions, Conflict and Peacebuilding (2021-2026) is a collaborative project with the Danish Institute for International Studies, Nyan Corridor, and the Regional Centre for Social Science and Sustainable Development at Chiang Mai University. The project aims to improve academic and policy understanding of climate change impacts and conflict dynamics in Myanmar's ethnic border regions. The team employs a blend of digital ethnography and in-situ fieldwork, collaborates with local researchers and organizations, and focuses on the study of customary land use, an intricate intersection of cultural and environmental interests.

Ekologos: Global Environmental Humanities (2022-2026) is a multi-continental collaboration funded by the Norwegian Agency for International Cooperation and Quality Enhancement in Higher Education, providing substantial opportunities for institute staff to engage in research in critical climate regions across different continents. By partnering with UiT The Arctic University of Norway, the Institute of Marine Research, Norway, the State University of Campinas UNICAMP, Brazil, RV University, Bangalore, and Doctors For You, Mumbai, the Highland Institute will strive to amplify the voices of local and indigenous communities disproportionately affected by climate change, blurring the lines between research and education, sciences and humanities, academic and traditional knowledge.

Furthermore, Earthkeepers, a project supported by Canada's International Development Research Centre (IDRC), seeks to document traditional ecological knowledge and climate change perceptions

along the Myanmar-Nagaland border. With a dedicated team headed by Catriona Child, Acting Director of the institute, it aims to facilitate discussions about climate justice and food security, while providing resources to address climatic and social challenges effectively. The Earthkeepers project is also committed to bolstering local research capacity, encouraging collaboration, and producing ethnographic materials to benefit all stakeholders.

While the journal values its editorial independence, we celebrate the institute's achievements, and very much look forward to exploring collaboration in publishing, including potential special journal issues. We especially anticipate the rich knowledge drawn from these significant multi-year and multi-dimensional projects requiring a platform for open access, peer-reviewed dissemination.

Shifting now to the present Highlander Journal volume 3, the opening article of this first issue, by Christian Poske, offers an incisive examination of the interactions between colonial administrators and their local interpreters in Nagaland. An ethnomusicologist by training, Poske's extensive fieldwork, guided by his discovery of a series of early Naga sound recordings on wax cylinders in the British Library, provides a fresh perspective on the continuing influence of colonial interactions on social hierarchy in Surumi, offering a unique viewpoint on the lasting impact of colonial domination and racial discrimination.

We then shift to Jop Koopman's insightful study on the transformative power of local legislature on the island of Lombok, Indonesia. Through the examination of *awiq-awiq*, a local practice that imposes heavy penalties for deforestation, Koopman provides a fascinating account of how the installation of such legislature has altered perceptions of sustainability and climate change in the region.

Contributing further to our exploration of the region's complexities, a captivating photo essay presents the lived experiences of recent rural-urban migrants in Nepal. This poignant pictorial account offers insights into the challenges these migrants face in accessing healthcare in urban settings, told through their own lenses and narratives.

This issue also features a comprehensive conference report on the Southeast Asian Frontier (SEAF) #1: Highlands, convened at the Department of Communication, Universitas Islam Indonesia (UII), Yogyakarta. The workshop, co-convened by researchers from various institutions, engaged a diverse group of participants from multiple countries and disciplines. The report provides a detailed account of the workshop proceedings, highlighting the crucial role of academic discourse in driving research and innovation.

The other contributions in this issue, including Catriona Child's thought-provoking perspective in "Irfan's Ghost" and Anna Notsu's insightful review of 'Reworking Culture: Relatedness, Rites, and Resources in Garo Hills, North East India', further enhance our exploration of cultural continuities and transformations in this issue.

Our commitment to publishing high quality open access, peer-reviewed research is echoed in each contribution to this issue, as it will be in each issue to follow. The journey ahead is full of possibilities, and we invite you to join us - as an author, reviewer, or indeed as you do now as a reader - as we continue to explore, in multidisciplinary and comparative fashion, state, culture, and social formation within and beyond Asia.

With warm regards,
Michael T. Heneise
Co-Editor

The Anecdote of Hutton's Dream: Responses of a Sumi Naga Family to J. H. Hutton's Cylinder Recordings

CHRISTIAN POSKE

In this article, I examine the meaning of the oral accounts of a Sumi Naga family whose narrations I heard in the village Surumi in Nagaland, where I conducted fieldwork with the wax cylinder recordings of the British administrator-anthropologist John Henry Hutton (1885-1968) in February 2022. In response to a song recording featuring the voice of his Sumi Naga interpreter Vikhepu Ayemi (d. 1919), two of Vikhepu's indirect descendants shared with me anecdotes on Hutton and their ancestor, including a dream they said that Hutton once had. Aligning Hutton's notes and other British colonial sources providing information on Naga interpreters with these oral accounts, I discuss how British colonial conceptions and Sumi traditional notions of social and cultural hierarchy influenced the interactions of the two men and examine what significance their connection has for Vikhepu's descendants today. I argue that Hutton's representation of Vikhepu serves as a means for the family to underline their longstanding involvement in governmental matters and thereby reaffirm their high social status and leadership role in the village of Surumi. Furthermore, the oral accounts seem to act as a mechanism for them to recollect differently and redraw the power relations that existed between Hutton and Vikhepu, as they reverse the notion of Vikhepu's subordinateness and, more generally, Naga subservience that emerges from Hutton's publications and other colonial sources. In a wider sense, my article thus throws light on the way how members of a Naga community process legacies of colonial domination and racial discrimination through the proposition of alternative oral histories that inform their collective remembering of past events.

Keywords: Nagaland, ethnomusicology, audiovisual archives, wax cylinder recordings, performing arts, oral history

Introduction

In recent decades, historians and anthropologists have become aware of the relevance of orally transmitted information about the past for the historiography of indigenous communities (Cruikshank 1994; Maiga 2009; Miller 2011). Recently, indigenous scholars have contributed to discourses on the theorization of the term "oral history" itself, pointing out that Western conventions of conceptualizing oral history and oral tradition as two different academic disciplines imply "a reading of [indigenous] oral histories

as false, unreliable, or the puerile imaginings of ‘the other’” (Mahuika 2019, 1).¹ Regarding South Asian communities, Western oral history research has focussed on diasporas so far (Hamlett et al. 2008; Herbert 2009; Raghuram et al. 2009; Raychaudhuri 2019), whereas, on the subcontinent itself, oral history has gained the attention of academics only quite recently.² Yet oral history research on ethnic minorities remains marginal in India, certainly not only due to language barriers but probably also because academic discourses sometimes neglect the internal historiographies of these communities. The troubled recent past of the wider Nagaland region³ (Nuh and Lasuh 2016), in particular, has led to the suppression and marginalization of Naga perspectives on the modern history of their communities, which has made oral history research in the region difficult and, at the same time, very important. Although the abating Indo-Naga conflict has made fieldwork more feasible in the Indian state of Nagaland in recent decades, little oral history research has been done in the region yet.⁴

In ethnomusicology, on the other hand, it has become a common research method to recirculate historical sound recordings among cultural heritage communities to make access to archival collections more equitable and evoke responses to recordings from communities (Toner 2003; Lobley 2010; Campbell 2014). As a result, ethnomusicologists have become, like historians and anthropologists, aware of the fact that such recordings are relevant not only because performing arts and oral traditions contribute to the continuity of culture, but also because they may contain information that can be in other ways of vital importance to the present, an example being indigenous land ownership claims supported by the content of archival sound recordings (Koch 2008).

As an ethnomusicologist, I applied the method of recirculating historical sound recordings in countries of origin for the first time during my PhD research, which concerned the field recordings of the Dutch ethnomusicologist Arnold Adriaan Bake (1899-1963) (Poske 2020). During my fieldwork, I reconnected musicians and dancers in Jharkhand, West Bengal, and Bangladesh with the sound and silent film recordings that Bake had made in these regions between 1931 and 1956, to evaluate their responses to the recordings and enhance Bake’s recording documentation. Between January and March 2022, I conducted another research project based on this method in Nagaland, this time with the cylinder recordings of the British administrator-anthropologist John Henry Hutton (1885-1968) (Poske, forthcoming). Hutton served in the British colonial administration of the Naga Hills district from the early 1910s to 1929 in a region that roughly corresponds to the territory of the Indian state of Nagaland today. Between 1914-19, he recorded the songs of five different Naga communities of the district. During the research project, I recirculated the recordings in Nagaland to elicit responses from listeners (Lobley 2010), documented their reactions on film, and used the information provided by them to enhance Hutton’s recording documentation. Due to time constraints, I conducted most listening sessions with members of different Naga communities in the state capital Kohima. Guided by Hutton’s recording notes, I also visited the villages of Khonoma (Kohima district) and Surumi (Zunheboto district), where I played the recordings to Angami and Sumi listeners. In Surumi, I played the recordings to two members of a Sumi family who shared with me anecdotes on Hutton’s interactions with one of their ancestors, Vikhepu Ayemi, which gave rise to this article. Rather unexpectedly, the family’s accounts thus brought my project into contact

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1. Oral history emerged as a field of research in the USA and UK in the mid-20th century. In the 1980s, the American oral historian Charles T. Morrissey thought of it as “a basic structured collection of spoken firsthand memories in an interview setting” (Sommer and Quinlan 2009, 1). In this article, I use the term in a more general sense as encompassing all processes of collecting oral information about the past and the recordings resulting therefrom.
 2. The Oral History Association of India was founded in 2013 (<https://ohai.info>, accessed 8.4.2023).
 3. The wider Nagaland region encompasses all territories inhabited by Naga communities, including the Indian state of Nagaland, parts of Assam, Arunachal Pradesh and Manipur, and parts of neighbouring Myanmar.
 4. A notable exception is the “Lest we forget” video series of the film collective TakeOne Nagaland, which is a documentation of oral accounts on the Naga independence movement and military violence (<https://www.youtube.com/@takeonenagaland2111/videos>, accessed 31.12.2022).

with the domain of oral history, a point that I will return to at the end of this article. Amongst others, their accounts included a dream they said that Hutton once had, which confronted me with the topic of Naga dream narration and interpretation, which I outline later in this article.

When we examine the relations between British colonial administrators and their Naga subjects, we must take into account the wider ideological frameworks that shaped British attitudes towards South Asians in the colonial period. Investigating the period of the British Raj (1858-1947), historian Thomas R. Metcalf points out that there was an enduring tension between the ideals of similarity and difference in how the British contemplated India, which shaped differing strategies of governance. He argues that “from 1858 to 1918, the ideas that most powerfully informed British conceptions of India and its people were those of India's ‘difference’” (Metcalf 1995, x).

The Naga Hills district, however, remotely located in the northeast of the subcontinent, was a world in itself, inhabited by minority communities whose ethnicities, cultures, indigenous religions, and ways of life were very different from those of the majority Hindu population and the larger religious minorities of mainland South Asia. Arguably, this was one of the reasons why British administrators like Hutton tended to see more similarities between themselves and the Nagas than with other South Asian communities. Thus, Hutton asserted that “[t]he least that can be said of the Naga is that in general he has mental outlooks and mental processes far more consonant with those of the European than has the ordinary native of India” (Hutton 1921a, 38), arguing that this was so because of the absence of the Hindu caste system. Cultural similarities, such as shared dietary preferences for non-vegetarian food, the absence of religious taboos on alcohol consumption, and the progressing conversion of Naga communities to the Christian faith arguably contributed to these notions of connectedness, which fostered friendships between British administrators and their Naga associates.

These companionships were often particularly close in the case of Naga interpreters who worked for the British administration for extended periods, sometimes over decades. Consequently, they became important informants for the ethnographic research of J. H. Hutton and other British administrator-anthropologists (Hutton 1921a, 1921b; Mills 1922, 1926, 1937). Sometimes, interpreters even became human models for visual representations of Naga culture created by British artists (Elliott 2014, 20-22). In these ways, Naga interpreters contributed to the production of representations of Naga cultures that are now at Western cultural and academic institutions, which inform our understanding of Naga cultures till today (Heneise and Moon-Little 2014, 1).

Nevertheless, we usually have very little detail about the personal interactions that took place between British administrators and their Naga associates, and the little we believe to know is, all too often, based on colonial writings articulated by defunct ideological frameworks (Wouters and Heneise 2017, 4). Sucharita Sen points out that in terms of British India, “[e]xisting literature on interracial relationships has largely oscillated between the two opposites of racial animosities and heterosexual intimacies” (Sen 2022, i), and that academic research neglected the large spectrum of interpersonal interactions that took place in other contexts. This article contributes to addressing this lacuna by discussing the interpersonal relations between Hutton and his Sumi Naga interpreter Vikhepu Ayemi.⁵

In the first section, I discuss how Hutton and British contemporaries represented Naga interpreters in their internal reports and published writings to see what conclusions these documents allow about the ground realities of the work of Naga interpreters and Hutton's relations to Vikhepu. Subsequently, I discuss the oral accounts of the Sumi Naga family I visited during my fieldwork, which offer an alternative perspective on the social hierarchies and resulting psychological dynamics that influenced the two men's interactions. In the following section, I place the oral accounts of the family in the context of the Naga practices of dream narration and interpretation and examine what meaning the accounts carry for the family. This leads me to my conclusion, where I reflect upon the implications of interpreting the family's accounts and my fieldwork in Surumi.

5. In the following, I refer to Vikhepu Ayemi with his first name “Vikhepu”.

The British perspective: colonial representations of Naga interpreters

In this section, I discuss how Hutton and other British writers represented Naga interpreters in their publications and other writings to examine which conclusions these sources allow on the ground realities of the daily work that Naga interpreters carried out in the British period, and on Hutton's relationship with his Sumi interpreter Vikhepu Ayemi. Written in the English language and originally intended for Western audiences, these sources today also provide educated Naga readers with extensive information on the traditional culture and the history of their communities, and on the complex web of interpersonal relations and allegiances that existed between Naga interpreters and British administrators like Hutton. Therefore, these sources are relevant to the question of how contemporary Naga society processes the legacy of British colonial rule, a point that I come back to later. In this section, I also probe what insights these sources contribute to the question how Hutton perceived his cultural situatedness as administrator and anthropologist posted in the Naga Hills district of British India at a time when Western colonial notions of racial hierarchy and political loyalty clashed with indigenous conceptions of individual rights, clan hierarchies, and community allegiances that had developed in Naga societies over the course of centuries.

With the colonization of Nagaland, Western cultural concepts of social and political structure made inroads into Naga society and began to influence the organization of village policies, setting off processes of social, political, and cultural change that continue till today (Wouters 2018). When the British began to colonize Nagaland in the 1830s, they first attempted to secure administrative control over the region through restrictive measures, then through military subjugation, and eventually through a more sophisticated system of indirect rule that used existing hierarchies of Naga societies (Jacobs et al. 2012, 24). Under this system, the British colonial administration employed influential individuals of Naga communities as *dobashi*-s, a term meaning "person speaking two languages". These were interpreters who acted as intermediaries between the administration and village communities, aiding the administration in the implementation of orders and giving them the feedback of village communities, a two-way process that led to relatively smooth governance. Another important role in the British administration of the Naga hills region was that of the *gaonbura*, meaning "village elder", which was also held by important members of village communities, who carried out administrative tasks on behalf of the British administration.⁶

Hutton joined the Indian Civil Service in 1909 and was transferred to the Naga Hills District in the early 1910s. In the following years, he was stationed as an Assistant Commissioner in Kohima and as a Subdivisional Officer in Mokokchung, after which he became Deputy Commissioner of the Naga Hills District in 1917. He retained the post until 1929 when he became Census Commissioner in Delhi, which he remained until 1933. During his administrative career, Hutton studied the societies and cultures of Naga communities and published articles on the topic from 1914 onwards (e.g., Hutton 1914, 1915, 1920). His first two monographs, *The Angami Nagas, With Some Notes on Neighbouring Tribes* (Hutton 1921a) and *The Sema⁷ Nagas* (Hutton 1921b) examine Angami and Sumi culture and society in detail. After his resignation from the Indian Civil Service in 1936, he returned to England, where he became a Lecturer in Social Anthropology and subsequently Professor of Social Anthropology at Cambridge University, a post he held until his retirement in 1950. In recognition of his research, he received numerous awards,

6. Jelle P. Wouters points out that "[t]he position of Gaonbura was introduced by the British who selected a number of persons in each village, whom they thought had considerable local influence [...]. They were bestowed with the [responsibility] to collect house-tax and to submit these to government offices, upon which they received a commission. They were also empowered to settle local disputes, and to notify the government in the event of any serious disturbances. Besides occasional commissions, they were also granted a red shawl to signal their allegiance to the British, and, in some instances, a gun. After the British departed from the Naga Hills, the position of Gaonbura was kept in place by the postcolonial government" (Wouters 2018, 129). As we will see in the example of Vikhepu Ayemi, the positions of *dobashi* and *gaonbura* sometimes converged in the same person.

7. Nowadays, community members refer to themselves as "Sumi".

including the Rivers Memorial Medal and awards from the Royal Society of Arts, the Asiatic Society of Bengal, and the Anthropologische Gesellschaft of Vienna. Today, the Pitt Rivers Museum (Oxford) and the Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology (Cambridge) hold numerous artefacts of Naga culture collected by Hutton, as well as his correspondence and official tour diaries.

These print and archival sources offer information on the work that Naga interpreters carried out on behalf of the British administration. Amongst others, there are notes on Hutton's interpreters in the obituaries that were written for him after his death. The obituary written by his second wife Maureen Margaret Hutton (née O'Reilly) includes the following quote on the reflections of an unnamed Naga interpreter:

An Indian colleague wrote "one of the old Sema Interpreters said 'Dr. Hutton was like a lamp in the Naga Hills during his service in that land.'" (M. M. Hutton 1968, 73)

Although the quote suggests that the interpreter remembered Hutton's tenure as having positive effects on the lives of Naga communities, the exact meaning of the statement attributed to him remains unclear. Perhaps, he thought that Hutton was a guiding light in a period of darkness and political turmoil, as the phrase "like a lamp" suggests. The obituary written by the British colonial administrator Charles Ridley Pawsey (1894-1972), on the other hand, provides some information on Hutton's interactions with his interpreters. Although Pawsey portrays these interactions as trustful and informal, different from the procedures that characterized the workings of the British administration in other regions of British India, he notably also ascribes physical violence to Hutton, which illustrates that despite the alleged air of informality, colonial hierarchies and a readiness to enact violence defined his conduct with Nagas:

In the Old Naga Hills there was always a feeling of mutual trust and friendship, direct access to the District Officer by word of mout[h] without the expense of a petition endorsed with an eight-anna stamp. An air of informality was prevalent in the Court room. In any case of importance the Court room would be packed, reeking with the smell of wood-fire smoke and rice beer and damp hair and clothes, with Naga Dobashis (the backbone of the administration) stating the claims of the parties. Nobody enjoyed this more than Hutton, who sought to preserve order with some noise himself, and occasional violence; for some years the stain on the office wall from a hurled bottle of ink was preserved by the Dobashis and pointed out as an awful example of what happened to recalcitrant litigants. Later to avoid material damage Hutton had a series of apparent pincushions at hand but these contained shot and varied in weight, and were used as ammunition according to the degree of recalcitrance shown by the witness or accused. On tour the atmosphere was even more informal... (Obituary for Hutton, Pawsey [1968?], 2-3, Pitt Rivers Museum, Hutton collection)

Hutton's tour diaries are perhaps the most important source of information on his interactions with Naga interpreters, elucidating his personal views and attitudes.⁸ Commissioned by the British colonial administration, the diaries include notes on the collection of taxes, the imposition of fines, the settlement of community disputes, and other aspects of Hutton's official duties in the district. Here, we find numerous entries illustrating that Naga interpreters not only facilitated communication with village communities and supervised actions ordered by the British. While this certainly constituted an important aspect of their employment for the administration, we find information that they also had to carry out menial tasks, some of which may have affected their social prestige in the eyes of Naga communities, as the following entry on a dispute between two Sumi Naga factions indicates:

8. The Pitt Rivers Museum holds Hutton's tour diaries from 1917-29 and 1934-35. A footnote in Hutton's first monograph suggests that he wrote tour diaries at least from September 1913 onwards (Hutton 1921a, 247), but the whereabouts of these early tour diaries remain unknown.

Apparently the foment was given an additional fillip some time ago – probably some years ago – by a quarrel in which one party quoted the authority of the dobashi Luzukhu for something. The other replied that Luzukhu was no dobashi but a scullion in Mokokchung kitchen.⁹
(J. H. Hutton, diary entry for 24.11.1920, Pitt Rivers Museum, Hutton collection, box 2)

Another entry from September 1921 illustrates that interpreters also had to take on other unpleasant tasks:

The village had a deserted air and is usually inhabited by mithan only who have trampled the village street into an almost unpassable morass of mud. The unfortunate dobashi who had to carry backwards and forwards through it – for there was no way round or across – sank literally knee-deep as he went along, and that for about 80 yards.
(J. H. Hutton, diary entry for 30.9.1921, Pitt Rivers Museum, Hutton collection, box 2)

Once, an interpreter even saved Hutton from danger of life, which further evinces the subservience of Naga interpreters to him:

Before reaching the pass I left the path for a yard or two and narrowly escaped a very nasty accident if not a sticky finish; the ground gave way suddenly under me and I was thrown violently forward, luckily, so that I managed with my outstretched arms to hang on my armpits on the far side of the pitfall and stay there balanced. I had gone through the leaves covering and concealing a trap which consisted in a deep hole about 10 ft. down with sides like a well. I was afraid of slipping in and being horribly spitted on panjis,¹⁰ but could not pull myself out and dare not move for fear of slipping back. I was a long way ahead of the coolies but luckily one dobashi was following pretty close and he came and pulled me out when he heard me singing murder, and then told me how a man of Setuho fell into such a pit he had dugged himself and was killed transfixed on his own panjis.
(J. H. Hutton, diary entry for 4.3.1935, Pitt Rivers Museum, Hutton collection, box 2)

Nevertheless, the inherent racism of colonial hierarchies shaped Hutton's interactions with his interpreters until the end of his career in the Indian Civil Service, despite the invaluable assistance that he received from them. Thus, he called the mass resignation of Sumi interpreters "a bluff", outlining a cool-headed strategy of replacement in this entry from 1934:

The Sema dobashis, being dissatisfied with an order of the S.D.O.'s resigned 'en bloc' – a piece of bluff, of course, which they will not get away with. Their places can be filled three times over with men every bit as good as they are tomorrow, but I told Sub-Divisional Office to keep them open till the end of the month anyway, to allow a chance to recant, and then to start replacing them, one at a time only, from the top.
(J. H. Hutton, diary entry for 18.-21.7.1934, Pitt Rivers Museum, Hutton collection, box 2)

Furthermore, the entry suggests that many Nagas aspired to secure employment as interpreters, arguably not only because the post provided an income, but also because it increased their social status in the eyes of many community members.

In his publications, Hutton generally writes in a respectful tone about his Naga interpreters, highlighting their contributions to his anthropological research. Arguably, he did so not only to do justice to their assistance in his research but also to present his research as informed by high ethical standards. Indeed, he refers to his interpreters repeatedly in his two Naga monographs *The Angami Nagas With Some Notes on*

9. Hutton's headquarters were in Mokokchung when he was Subdivisional Officer from 1915-17.

10. *Panji-s* were sharpened bamboo sticks that Nagas placed at the bottom of earthen pits for defensive purposes (Hutton 1921b, 24).

Neighbouring Tribes (1921a, 38, 168, 247) and *The Sema Nagas* (1921b, 29, 161, 249, 303, 363-64), which suggests that they contributed significantly to his research. He acknowledges this input in the prefaces and through a footnote in the first monograph (1921a, viii, 247; 1921b, viii).

Sections of the two works indicate that Hutton's Sumi interpreter Vikhepu Ayemi played a particularly significant role in his research on Naga culture and that the two men were connected on an intellectual level. In the preface of his second monograph, Hutton thus highlights Vikhepu's contributions:

Last, but far from least, I have to mention my Sema friends who have been the real means of my making what record I could of tribal customs – Vikhepu, Chief of the Ayemi Clan in Seromi, Inato, Chief of Lumitsami, Khupu of Lazemi, Nikiye of Nikiye-nagami, Hezekhu of Sheyepu, Mithihe of Vekohomi, Hoito of Sakhalu, Ivikhu of Lizmi, Inzhevi of Yepthomi, Hoito of Kiyeshe, and many others, but the first five or six in particular... [M]y indebtedness for information to Vikhepu, four years my personal Sema interpreter at Mokokchung, was particularly great, and his death in the influenza epidemic of 1918¹¹ was a grave loss to the district. (Hutton 1921b, viii)

Correspondingly, he credits Vikhepu as one of the two main sources for the Sumi folk tales published in the second monograph (1921b, 303-61). Notably, he describes Vikhepu as “one of the most intelligent Semas I ever knew” (1921a, 404) and “a chief and a man of superior intellect” (1921b, 303), which suggests that he respected him not only because of his status in Sumi society but also on account of his intellectual capacities. Amongst other notes on Vikhepu, the second monograph includes a footnote that proves that he shared with Hutton details about the extramarital affair of a Sumi village chief (1921b, 206), which suggests that there must have been some camaraderie between Hutton and Vikhepu, as otherwise, Vikhepu would have not shared such sensitive personal information with Hutton. In the book, we also find a detailed genealogy chart of Vikhepu's ancestry, based on information provided by himself (144; second family tree following the page).

If we look at the visual representations of Naga culture in Hutton's Naga monographs (1921a, 1921b), we find that both works feature eye-catching coloured frontispieces contributing to their aesthetic appeal. The first monograph features a portrait of an Angami warrior and the second one a portrait of Vikhepu Ayemi in ceremonial attire, holding a spear and a shield.¹² One of Hutton's photographs from the Pitt Rivers Museum Oxford [PRM] (Fig. 1) and a half-coloured sketch from the Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology Cambridge [MAA] (Fig. 2) suggest that Vikhepu's portrait (Fig. 3) is derived from Hutton's photograph.

The clarity of the photograph suggests that Hutton took it with Vikhepu's permission, while its natural ambience evokes a notion of primordality, in line with the romanticized notion of traditional Naga culture that we find in sections of Hutton's publications where he deplores the loss of culture effected by Westernization and Christianization (e.g., 1921a, vii-viii).¹³ Nevertheless, he regarded Western civilization as superior and thought it was its task to carefully guide Nagas on the path to progress because he regarded them as “savage races” (1921a, 177) whose culture was “primitive” (397).

Overall, the sources that I have referred to in this section leave no doubt that Hutton regarded himself as superior to his Naga interpreters not only because of his social status as a representative of the British colonial administration but also culturally and intellectually because he considered himself a member of an advanced civilization that had reached a higher level on the ladder of human evolution. Regarding Vikhepu Ayemi, we can summarize that he was an important associate of Hutton who not only assisted

11. According to his descendants, Vikhepu Ayemi died in 1919.

12. On the portrait, the shield is oriented upside-down, with the square end on top and decorated with a plume of goat's hair, which indicates ceremonial use (Hutton 1921b, 25).

13. The visual representations of Nagas on the covers and frontispieces of Hutton's and Mills' monographs can be regarded as an exoticization of Naga culture, as Westernization had already led to changes in the clothing of Nagas by the turn of the century (Shakespeare 2021).

Figure 1: “Vikhepu of Seromi”
(PRM 1998.221.42.9)

Figure 2: Partially hand-
coloured black and white
photograph (MAA P.59429.
HUT)

Figure 3: “Vikhepu, Chief of
the Ayemi Clan in Seromi”¹⁴
(Hutton 1921b, coloured
frontispiece)

him as an interpreter but also contributed significantly to his research on Naga culture. Moreover, Hutton’s respectful comments hint at a personal friendship between the two men, which raises the question of how conceptions of Naga hierarchies and British hierarchies influenced their interactions. It also opens the question of how contemporary Sumi Naga society assesses the social relationship that existed between the two men, a point that I address in the following section.

The Sumi perspective: Hutton’s dream and other anecdotes from Surumi

During his tenure in Nagaland, Hutton made fourteen cylinder recordings, which he sent to the Pitt Rivers Museum in Oxford. During the research project that I conducted on the recordings in early 2022, I visited the Museum in the month of January to examine the inserts that Hutton had sent with the cylinders to Oxford. This enabled me to identify Vikhepu Ayemi (d. 1919) as one of the singers whose voice is audible on Hutton’s cylinder recording No. 14 (Poske, forthcoming). The following month, I travelled to Nagaland to conduct my fieldwork with the recordings. Because of information I had found on the insert of cylinder recording No. 14, I decided to visit Vikhepu’s home village Surumi to locate his descendants and play the recording to them.¹⁵ Lanuakum Aier, an Ao Naga researcher of the Highland Institute in Kohima, contacted the headman of the village via telephone with the help of a Sumi intern of the Institute, who called the headman. Lanuakum and I received permission for our visit and after all logistics had been arranged, we were on our way from Kohima to Surumi a few days later. We travelled via Mokokchung, a six-hour drive from Kohima. During our lunch break at a roadside restaurant, Lanuakum informally introduced me to the practice of Naga dream narration, telling me that before I had notified him of my plan to visit Surumi, he had dreamed of visiting his relatives in Mokokchung. A few hours later,

14. Hutton attributes the creation of the portrait to Ms A. M. Grace from Hove (Hutton 1921b, viii). Today, the village is called “Surumi”.

15. Hutton’s recording note states: “Mithan cutting song at Sema harvest festival[:] Vikhepu Mithihe Nikiye Hoito Hezekhu” (insert of cylinder No. 14, Hutton collection, Pitt Rivers Museum). The names of these five interpreters appear in the preface of *The Sema Nagas* (Hutton 1921b, viii).

we arrived in the town. After an overnight stay in a hotel on a hill overlooking the town, we picked up his cousin Suneplong and departed for Surumi at dawn (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Sunrise in Mokokchung (Mokokchung, 19.2.2022; photo: author)

We arrived in Surumi two hours later, where we were welcomed by the headman's son, Vikishe. He brought us to the *achükaki*, the kitchen and dining room of the family, a large room with a stone hearth on the one side and a large wooden table with benches on the other. We held the listening sessions and interviews that would follow at this table, assisted by Vikishe who translated between English and the Sumi language. We began with Vikishe's father Qheniho Jakhalu (b. 1964), who turned out to be Vikhepu Ayemi's grandnephew.¹⁶ Qheniho holds the post of *akükatou* (head of the village chiefs) in Surumi today, a designation that has replaced the title of Head GB (principal *gaonbura*).¹⁷ During our meeting, he wore a red vest, a garment that has largely replaced the red shawl that used to be worn by *gaonbura*-s to signify their post (cf. Fig. 3). Apparently, he wore the vest because he had to attend a village council meeting on that day, though possibly, his choice of clothing was also connected to the purpose of our visit. With him, he brought a framed print of Vikhepu Ayemi's portrait from Hutton's monograph *The Sema Nagas* (Hutton 1921b) (Fig. 5).

For the listening sessions that followed, we set up a laptop for playing back Hutton's recordings through headphones and a camcorder for filming the reactions of participants. We began Qheniho's listening session with Hutton's cylinder recording No. 14 (Fig. 6).¹⁸ We informed him beforehand that he would listen to a recording featuring the voice of his granduncle Vikhepu and four other Sumi interpreters of Hutton. Although Qheniho initially seemed confused by the crackling background noise of the recording, he soon began to nod, as if recognizing something familiar. After taking off the headphones, he explained to us that the song on the recording was an *aza'shü'le*, a type of song that is performed to express honour or respect, and that it is performed in Surumi till today. Although Hutton's note from the cylinder insert suggests that the recorded song was connected to a ritual *mithun* sacrifice at a Sumi harvest festival, Qheniho

16. Qheniho is the grandson of Vikhepu's brother Vihoto.

17. In 2017, the Sumi Kukami Hoho ("Council of Sumi Village Chiefs") substituted the title *gaonbura* with the title *akükau* ("village chief") as the official designation of hereditary village leaders to distinguish them clearly from government-appointed *gaonbura*-s. Correspondingly, the title of Head GB was replaced with the title *akükatou* (head of the village chiefs) (<https://morungexpress.com/sumis-replace-usage-gb-akukau>, accessed 19.12.2022).

18. <https://soundcloud.com/pittriversound-1/mithan-cutting-song-from>, accessed 18.8.2022.

Figure 5: Qheniho Jakhalu with print of Vikhepu’s portrait from *The Sema Nagas* (Hutton 1921b) The title of the print reads: “Vikhepu G.B.,¹⁹ Chief of the Ayemi Clan in Surumi” (Surumi, 19.2.2022; photo: author)

could not associate the piece with any ritual or festival but said that it could have been performed on any festive occasion.²⁰

Figure 6: Qheniho Jakhalu listening to Hutton’s cylinder recordings The name badge on the red vest reads: “Qheniho Jakhalu, Head G.B. Surumi” (Surumi, 19.2.2022; photo: author)

19. The abbreviation “G.B.” stands for *gaonbura* (“village headman”), a post given to Vikhepu by the British administration.

20. During the subsequent interview, Qheniho speculated that the honoured person could have been Hutton himself. Later, he suggested that this type of song was also related to warfare. The exact meaning of the song remains unclear.

In the interview that followed the listening session, I asked Qheniho about the connection of his granduncle Vikhepu Ayemi to Hutton. After outlining the ancestry of his family, Qheniho pointed out that Vikhepu himself did not have any direct descendants because his only son died as an infant from the Spanish Flu, as did Vikhepu's wife and eventually he himself.²¹ Qheniho then told us that Vikhepu assisted the British administration as an interpreter from 1909-10 to 1919, which suggests that he had held the post already before Hutton's tenure in Nagaland began. Furthermore, Qheniho pointed out that in his capacity as interpreter, Vikhepu was not in charge of collecting taxes but acted as a spokesperson for his people because he could speak Nagamese and Hindi, apart from his mother tongue, the Sumi language. Moreover, he told us that Vikhepu did not join the British army to fight in Europe during World War One, like many Sumi men did, because of his post as an interpreter for the British administration.

During the interview, we handed over to Qheniho a printout of the photograph that had served as a template for Vikhepu's portrait in *The Sema Nagas* (1921b), a gesture that was appreciated by him because he was unaware of the fact that the portrait was based on a photograph. When we went through the names of the other four interpreters who also participated in the recording, as the cylinder inlay suggests, Qheniho recognized one of the names but was unfamiliar with the other three. Moreover, he expressed his gratitude for Hutton's anthropological research because of the knowledge his family has gained from his works, a comment that broadly seemed to refer to the information on Sumi culture that Hutton provides in his monograph *The Sema Nagas* (1921b). Qheniho then explained how the right to the post of village headman was passed down through hereditary kinship from Vikhepu's father Hekshe via Vikhepu and Vikhepu's younger brother Vihoto to himself.²² At one point, Qheniho asked for permission to make a remark, and then shared the following anecdote:

Hutton was [British] and he was so brave... After J. H. Hutton came here, he came to notice that Vikhepu was so brave among the Sumis [...], so courageous, and then [...] he tried to become good friend with Vikhepu. Sir J. H. Hutton, after knowing [Vikhepu] properly [...], he told Vikhepu not to [address] him as "Sir", but to [address] him as a friend. In 1916, Hutton appointed Vikhepu as a chief [gaonbura] and then opened his own [i.e., Vikhepu's] private office for the village. [...] Red blanket was issued. I am sure you know what the red blanket means? Red blanket is all about the people who... [At this point, Vikishe pointed to the red vest that Qheniho wore and said "Yes, this is the one... during that time, it was like a blanket, na?"] That blanket was issued from here, [the one] which was given by J. H. Hutton to Vikhepu, and [Vikhepu] was told to issue that blanket [...]. [T]hat blanket was worn only by the chiefs, the G.B.s. Four to five tribes [from] Nagaland, they came [to] this very place and took that red blanket. (interview with Qheniho Jakhalu, Surumi, 19.2.2022)

After the interview, Qheniho and Vikishe led us to a tree in front of the family's kitchen and dining room (Fig. 7), where we were told that J. H. Hutton and Vikhepu Ayemi had planted it together as a symbol of their friendship before Vikhepu's death. According to the family, Hutton came to Surumi to hold a speech at Vikhepu's funeral. Qheniho then excused himself, as he had to leave for a village council meeting that took place that day.

During the lunch break, Vikishe showed me a copy of the booklet *Sürü Xülhe* ("The History of Surumi") (Shikhu et al. 2021), written in the Sumi language and published by the village council in 2021. Apart from details on previous and current administrative organizations and cultural activities of the village,

21. After the death of his wife, Vikhepu planned to remarry but passed away before he could do so (personal conversation with Qheniho Jakhalu, 19.2.2022).

22. Qheniho pointed out that like Vikhepu, Hekshe and Vihoto had been *dobashi-s* and *gaonbura-s*.

Figure 7: Branchless tree (right), planted by J. H. Hutton and Vikhepu Ayemi, in front of the *achükaki* (kitchen and dining room, centre left) (Surumi, 19.2.2022; photo: author)

the booklet features a section on notable historical events, which includes a half page displaying Vikhepu Ayemi's portrait from *The Sema Nagas* with a reference to the monograph.²³

After the lunch break, I held a listening session with Heshevi Awomi (b. 1945 or 1946), the widow of Vikhepu's nephew Hokiye.²⁴ We first played to her Hutton's cylinder recording No. 14, the same recording that her son Qheniho had just heard. After taking off the headphones, she said that she could not understand the song because it was sung in the *tuku* dialect, and that this was a dialect of Sumi music that differed considerably from their vernacular. Nevertheless, she was familiar enough with this type of song to state that it was traditional, performed by men only, and still practised today. Like Qheniho, she associated the song with festivals.

Subsequently, I played to her two other Sumi songs recorded by Hutton, an agricultural work song (cylinder recording No. 9: "Ishi no ghi sholu"; Hutton 1921b, 116) and a song praising a warrior (cylinder recording No. 13: "Inato-no Likelio i-pfu-ghe"; Hutton 1921b, 177-78, 363, 370). After listening to these, she said that the melodies reminded her of songs she had heard in her childhood when working in the fields. I then returned to the topic of cylinder recording No. 14, interested in her thoughts on Vikhepu's participation. I asked her how she felt about the fact that Hutton had recorded the voice of her uncle. She politely replied that she was grateful to have the opportunity to listen to the recordings. Unsatisfied with this reply, I enquired if she thought that it was a good thing that Hutton had recorded Vikhepu, which induced her to share two anecdotes with me. After hearing the first one, Vikishe laughed and hesitated to speak, seemingly embarrassed to translate what he had just heard from his grandmother. He then translated her anecdote:

Vikhepu was the *dobashi*.. who worked under J. H. Hutton. So, whenever they [were] in the office together, whatever dispute it [was]..., whenever they [were] together, J. H. Hutton, whenever he was about to write, whenever [Vikhepu] was in the office, he used to shake, out of nervousness maybe,

23. The inclusion of the portrait in the booklet is significant because it illustrates how a visual representation of Sumi Naga culture from one of Hutton's monographs has become a means for a Sumi village community to represent itself to others.

24. Hokiye was the son of Vikhepu's younger brother Vihoto.

but we are not sure..., maybe out of nervousness. In the presence of Vikhepu, he used to shiver. [That is], at first, before they became close friend[s], because Vikhepu... worked under him, right? [...] J. H. Hutton, he was so confused, because whenever he [was] in the presence of Vikhepu, when they [were] in the same office, [at] the same table, he used to shiver. (Interview with Heshevi Awomi, Surumi, 19.2.2022)

She then told another anecdote about a dream that Hutton once had. When she described how Hutton saw Vikhepu high above him in his dream, she gesticulated excitedly with her hands (Fig. 8):

One fine day, J. H. Hutton got a dream... [In] his dream, he saw Vikhepu in a three-storey building on the third [storey], and [Hutton] was just on the ground floor, watching him... In his dream, [Hutton] saw [it] like that. So, he came to [the] realization, in his own realization...[that] under the government rule, he is the head, but [in] this very area, in this very location...,²⁵ he realized that he is never above Vikhepu. That's what he assumed after his dream.... So, after that [...], on that very day, [Vikhepu] was given the power of kingship in this very area.²⁶ [...] After that, J. H. Hutton [gave] permission, and then gave his power to Vikhepu.²⁷ [...] He was given the power to rule, and he was told that he [i.e., Hutton] wouldn't be interrupting. (ibid.)

Figure 8: Heshevi Awomi narrating the anecdote of Hutton's dream (Surumi, 19.2.2022; photo: Suneplong Imchen)

25. Here, Heshevi presumably referred to the wider Surumi region.

26. Perhaps, the phrase "was given the power of kingship in this very area" referred to the village community's act of bestowing the post of *akükatou* (village headman) to Vikhepu. According to Vikishe, the village of Surumi was founded by nine Sumi clans and only two of these, the Ayemi and Awomi clans, are eligible to nominate candidates for the post of the *akükatou*, which they occupy in turns (personal conversation with Vikishe Jakhlu, 10.12.2022).

27. The phrase "[Hutton] gave his power to Vikhepu" could refer to Hutton's act of bestowing the post of *gaonbura* to Vikhepu. Formally, the District Magistrate was in charge of appointing *gaonbura*-s, but Hutton was only Subdivisional Officer in 1916. Therefore, Hutton must have conferred the title upon Vikhepu in the name of the District Magistrate.

When I asked Heshevi how she came to know about the story and the dream, she replied that she had learned about them from her forefathers, and that she thought Hutton probably had not told the dream to Vikhepu, but rather to someone else. This implies that her forefathers got to know about Hutton's dream narration indirectly through an intermediary, possibly one of their family members. I contented myself with these details and refrained from asking further questions about the origin of her anecdotes, to avoid raising the impression of questioning their authenticity. Satisfied with these surprising responses to Hutton's recordings, I concluded the listening session shortly after.

After another meeting with Qheniho in the afternoon, we thanked our hosts for their participation in our project, packed up, and left for Mokokchung. The following day, we travelled back to Kohima. After our return, I realized that I had heard two dream narrations within the span of three days, which seemed remarkable. Was it possible that Lanuakum's dream experience had foreshadowed future events, just like Hutton's dream had done? A few weeks later, when I began to catalogue my field recordings at home in Kolkata, I started to evaluate the accounts of Qheniho and Heshevi.

Interpreting the oral accounts of Vikhepu's descendants

In what follows, I offer an interpretation of the anecdotes on Hutton and Vikhepu that I heard in Surumi, paying particular attention to how the anecdote of Hutton's dream is related to traditional Naga practices of dream narration and interpretation. In doing so, I largely disregard the question of whether their oral accounts are based on real historical events or not, as it is not my intention to judge the veracity of the accounts that Qheniho and Heshevi shared with me. Rather, I try to arrive at an understanding of what meaning the anecdotes carry for the family, and, in a wider sense, consider what deductions this allows about how contemporary Naga society might process its colonial past.

It is important to bear in mind that Hutton had a considerable interest in Naga practices of dream narration and interpretation because this fact may help us understand why and how Sumi community members got to know about one of his dream experiences. In his first monograph, he speaks of the Angami "science of dreaming" and explains Angami practices of dream interpretation (Hutton 1921a, 246-47), recounting a premonitory dream that one of his Angami interpreters shared with him on one of his tours through the Naga Hills district (247). His second monograph includes some details on dream interpretation as practised in Sumi culture. Amongst others, Hutton discusses the role of *thumomi*-s, individuals that he characterizes as "seers" or "witches" (Hutton 1921b, 213). According to Hutton, a *thumomi* is "an intermediary between private persons and the spirits" and a "dreamer of dreams and skilled in the interpretation thereof, a curer of illness, and a discoverer of stolen property" (Hutton 1921b, 232). The monograph includes two photographs of *thumomi*-s, both of them women (plate facing page 232). On the topic of dream interpretation, Hutton also held correspondence with the British physician and anthropologist Charles Gabriel Seligman (1873-1940), who was influenced by the theory of "dream types", developed by Sigmund Freud (1856-1939).²⁸ In one of his letters to Seligman, Hutton thus describes a dream he once had at a government bungalow in Baimho, which led him to empirically test the villagers' claim that the place was haunted (Heneise 2018, 14-15). These references to Naga dream culture in Hutton's publications and correspondence suggest that he spoke about dreams and dream interpretation with his Naga interpreters from time to time, and perhaps even shared some of his own dream experiences with them.

28. The Hutton Collection of the Pitt Rivers Museum includes a comparative chart of Naga dream symbols, compiled by Hutton, arguably for C. G. Seligman. The chart includes numerous examples of Angami and Sumi dream symbols with interpretation and informants' names (Hutton Collection, Pitt Rivers Museum, box 3). The chart includes the names of two Sumi informants, Inzhevi and Viyito. Apparently, Inzhevi was one of Hutton's Sumi interpreters (Hutton 1921b, viii). The chart also includes comparisons to dream symbolism in Irish legends and literature. Hutton came from a family with Irish ancestry.

Although the traditional practices of dream narration and interpretation continue to play an important role in Naga society today, there is only one monograph on the topic yet, which focuses on dream narration and interpretation as practised in Angami society (Heneise 2018). With his study, Heneise demonstrates that Angami dream culture is “fundamentally social in nature”, as “[d]reams are understood as messages for the community” (50). He reports that “daily dream sharing is a practice most common among women, and particularly among married women, mothers and their daughters, and among female neighbours” (43). Furthermore, Heneise points out that “[d]ream narratives connected to significant family events are remembered and passed down through several generations, sometimes achieving mythical status within the clan. Such narratives, in turn, become important elements in shaping group identity [and] give a sense of divine purpose to clan members...” (5-6). Considering the continued transmission of the anecdote of Hutton's dream within Heshevi's family, we can surmise that much of this holds true in the context of Sumi society, too.

Furthermore, we need to consider the fact that the Nagaland region witnessed profound social and cultural change in the British period and after Indian independence, which raises the question of why Naga practices of dream narration and interpretation continue to endure till the present day. In her study of dream interpretation in modern Egypt, Almira Mittermaier points out that dreams may “matter even (and maybe especially) in a time of war, emergency laws, and social disintegration *not* because they provide dreamers with a protective blanket of false consciousness or hallucinatory wish fulfillment, but because they insert the dreamer into a wider network of symbolic debts, relationships, and meanings” (Mittermaier 2011, 2-3). As Vikhepu was an associate of the British colonial administration in a time of rapid social and cultural change, this statement provides a possible angle for understanding why the anecdote of Hutton's dream has become so relevant amongst Vikhepu's descendants that it has been orally transmitted till today.

Regarding my fieldwork, one of the questions that come to mind is what influence my identity and positionality as a Western researcher had on my interview participants. Was it my cultural background that had triggered Qheniho and Heshevi to share with me anecdotes questioning British colonial narratives on the power relations that existed between Hutton and Vikhepu? Would they have given the same answers to a Naga researcher? Although I was assisted by two Ao Nagas in Surumi, the fact that I was the principal investigator and interviewer must have had some effect on Qheniho and Heshevi – at least it did on Vikishe, who appeared somewhat intimidated by our recording set-up. I was the interviewer, and they were the respondents. Despite the well-crafted project outline and elaborately formulated information sheets and consent forms that I used to avoid possible ethical concerns, this fact was an uncomfortable reminder that some of my project aims were of a similarly extractive nature like Hutton's research: Nagas shared with me elements of their intangible cultural heritage that I would evaluate for academic publications to advance my career. Yet the unidirectional nature of my questioning was interrupted once during the two interviews, namely when Qheniho and Heshevi told me anecdotes about Hutton and Vikhepu. In some way, this act of unsolicited speaking seemed to question the power relations between us, just as the narrative content of their anecdotes questioned the existence of a top-bottom hierarchy between Hutton and Vikhepu. While this parallel may have been a coincidence, it certainly reminds us that thoughts of colonial injustice reverberate into the present in the collective memory of cultural heritage communities and that these may influence their reactions and responses to questions about their history.

Another important point to consider is the spatial setting of the interviews. We held both interviews in the kitchen and dining room of the family, which has a hearth on the kitchen side (Fig. 9). This setting is significant because, in Naga households, the hearth constitutes not only a place of domestic labour and food production but also of social interaction and conversation, including acts of dream narration and interpretation. Referring to Angami society, Heneise writes:

Secondly, the hearth is the centre of omen interpretation, whether those omens are observed in waketime or in dreams. The hearth is where they are shared and discussed before they circulate beyond the household. Here new information obtained in dreams can often override the clan laws, and thus is a form of emergent authoritative knowledge that does not necessarily correspond

with clan genealogical knowledge. The alternatives that new forms of knowledge and information contribute form a dialectic to the conservatism of patriarchy, and this back-and-forth dynamic plays out daily in community life. (Heneise 2018, 80-81)

Considering Surumi, we can discern that indeed, patriarchal hierarchies seem to have played a role in the way how the two interviews were arranged: Qheniho, the male head of the family and headman of the village council, was our first participant, whereas Heshevi's interview took place later. Arguably, sharing the dream anecdote was a means for her to propagate her perspective on Hutton's interactions with her uncle Vikhepu.²⁹

Figure 9: Heshevi Awomi with relatives in front of the kitchen hearth (Surumi, 19.2.2022; photo: Suneplong Imchen)

Let us now consider the meaning of the narrative content of the anecdotes. Qheniho's anecdote portrayed Vikhepu and Hutton as close friends, an assumption supported by the existence of the tree planted by them that outlasted their lives. Notably, Qheniho's account characterizes Hutton as the person seeking to be associated with Vikhepu, rather than vice versa, implying that Vikhepu had a higher social status than Hutton – at least from the viewpoint of the Sumi community. Similarly, his account of Vikhepu formally appointing other village chiefs as *gaonbura-s* in Surumi suggests that his granduncle had a high social status in Sumi society and was an influential associate of the British administration. If we consider the facts that Qheniho owns a print of Vikhepu's portrait from Hutton's monograph *The Sema Nagas* with an added abbreviation signifying his granduncle's post ("G.B.") and that the portrait features in the booklet *Sürü Xülhe*, we can surmise that Qheniho uses these historical references to support his administrative leadership claims in the village today. In this context, it is important to note that in the personality of Qheniho, Sumi hereditary and governmental leadership roles converge, as was the case with

29. Hokishe Sema characterizes the Awomis as the priest clan of the Sumi community, perhaps one of the reasons why it was Heshevi who narrated the anecdote of Hutton's dream. Under the heading "Awomi the priests", Sema writes: "[Naga] priests performed rites in all ceremonies and festivals of the village. They are highly respected in societies and they are placed second to the chiefs in societies. They also foretell the future events and thus guide the life of the village." (Sema 1986, 169).

his granduncle Vikhepu, his great-grandfather Hekshe, and his grandfather Vihoto, all of whom were hereditary Sumi leaders as well as *dobashi*-s and *gaonbura*-s appointed by the British administration.³⁰

Heshevi's anecdotes, on the other hand, focussed more on the psychological aspects of Vikhepu's interactions with Hutton. The first anecdote portrayed Vikhepu as a personality exuding an overwhelming charisma on his surroundings, causing Hutton to shiver in his presence, an image standing in striking contrast to Pawsey's description of Hutton's dominant and violent conduct with his Naga subjects. To decipher the more complex meaning of the dream anecdote, it is helpful to recapitulate its basic outline: Hutton experiences a dream in his sleep and then interprets it. Prompted by his interpretation, he adjusts his actions in the waking world, based on the insights that his dream has offered him. This sequence of experiences and actions is reminiscent of Naga dream culture, which is characterized by the pattern of dream experience, narration, interpretation, and adjustment of actions in the waking world (Heneise 2018, 5). The only notable difference is that Heshevi's anecdote skipped the part of Hutton narrating his dream,³¹ which was substituted by Heshevi's re-narration of its content. This raises questions about the agency of Hutton. Perhaps, the dream experience originated not from him but from someone else? Thus, a possible trajectory could have been that one of Heshevi's ancestors had the dream and then narrated it to their relatives, who ascribed it to Hutton at a later point in time through processes of projection (Franz 1980). While this seems like a plausible possibility, we need to keep in mind that dream interpretation occurs in many cultures, including the Irish (Ettlinger 1948), to which Hutton was connected through his ancestry. Thence, he may have been familiar with Irish traditional practices of dream interpretation before his tenure in Nagaland, where he then experienced and interpreted one of his dreams, as described in Heshevi's anecdote.

Like Qheniho's account, Heshevi's anecdote of Hutton's dream concerns acts of power bestowal. Yet there is a significant difference: in Qheniho's anecdote, Vikhepu bestows power on behalf of the British administration, while in Heshevi's anecdote, power is bestowed upon Vikhepu by the Sumi community and the British administration. In her anecdote, Hutton's dream experience appears to foreshadow the village community's action of appointing Vikhepu as a chief. Retrospectively recognizing the connection between his dream experience and this action of the village community, Hutton bestows special administrative powers upon Vikhepu and allows him to rule over the Surumi region without British interference as a quasi-autonomous leader. Thereby, the dream anecdote portrays the Sumi people, embodied in the personality of Vikhepu, as able to withstand the dominant forces of British colonialism on account of their inherent character strength and moral superiority - at least in the Surumi region. The dream symbolism supports this interpretation, with the difference in elevation between the two men suggesting that Vikhepu's social status as village headman of Surumi and Sumi clan leader surpassed Hutton's rank as Subdivisional Officer of the British colonial administration by far. Arguably, Vikhepu's appearance on the third floor of a multi-storey building connotes his involvement in the affairs of the British administration, as traditional Naga architecture is characterized by single-storey constructions (Hutton 1921a, 50ff.; 1921b, 38ff.).

Linguistically, my interviews with Qheniho and Heshevi were hampered by my inability to speak the Sumi language and by Vikishe's limited English vocabulary, which constrained his choice of words during the interpretation of our interviews. Nevertheless, his usage of the term "kingship" appears peculiar, which he seemed to employ to denote Vikhepu's position as the headman of the village of Surumi, or perhaps as the leader of the wider Surumi region, in any case, a small geographical expanse hardly justifying use of the expression "kingship", a concept that is strictly speaking not part of traditional Sumi society,³² and, moreover, usually understood as referring to the leadership of larger polities. We can surmise, then, that

30. Personal conversation with Qheniho Jakhalu, 19.2.2022.

31. Arguably, Hutton must have narrated his dream to someone, as otherwise knowledge of the dream could not have been transmitted within Heshevi's family.

32. Traditional Sumi culture does not know the concept of kingship as such but is characterized by hereditary aristocratic leadership structures that provide the foundation for village chieftainship (Wouters 2018, 127-28; Hutton 1921b, 150).

Vikishe chose the term “kingship” not only for want of a more suitable English word but also because he wanted to express that Vikhepu’s exceptional prestige and social standing transcended cultural barriers and hence overrode the social hierarchies of British India.

The fact that Qheniho’s and Heshevi’s anecdotes have been transmitted orally within the family since the early 20th century suggests that they have considerable relevance to the family because they contribute to their self-understanding of their social and cultural identity. Specifically, the anecdotes seem to contribute to the family’s self-understanding of their social status in the village of Surumi and within Sumi society, and to the ways how they remember the relations of their ancestors to the British colonial administration. In this regard, the anecdote of Hutton’s dream appears particularly relevant, not only because it highlights Vikhepu’s high social status in Sumi society and his association with the British administration, but even more so because it presents a counter-perspective to Hutton’s implicit statements on the power relations between him and his Naga subjects: Hutton represents them as subordinates, but the dream anecdote inverts this relation and elevates Vikhepu to a higher social standing.

Although it remains unclear to what extent the family has engaged with Hutton’s publications, some of them are certainly aware of Hutton’s second monograph, as Qheniho’s ownership of a print of Vikhepu’s portrait indicates. This and the portrait’s inclusion in the booklet *Sürü Xülhe* illustrate that there is a sense of pride among him and his family members about the fact that Hutton included a portrait of their ancestor in a monograph that has become a reference work on Sumi culture. Yet in a more subtle sense, they may perceive the existence of the portrait as testifying a subordinating act of human objectification because Vikhepu makes his appearance as a human exhibit, captured on paper and devoid of agency. Possibly, this notion has contributed to the family’s sense that their perspectives on the two men’s interactions need to be conveyed to future generations as a counter-perspective to Hutton’s publications, which may have led to the continued transmission of the anecdotes within the family. We can surmise that for them, the same dichotomy of meaning may apply to Hutton’s sound recording of Vikhepu, which immortalized his voice and made him an object of research at the same time.

Are the family’s oral accounts, then, a manifestation of a revisionist perspective on the colonial history of Nagaland that challenges Hutton’s representation of colonial hierarchies in the Naga Hills district? Are their accounts just the expression of an inferiority complex that has led to wishful thinking about an ancestor who withstood the subjugating forces of the British Empire? This interpretation would certainly perpetuate colonial patterns of thinking by presuming that Western written sources are automatically more credible than the oral accounts of an indigenous community. After all, many details about the day-to-day realities of British rule over the Naga Hills district remain unclear, including the question of to what extent the workings of the colonial administration pervaded into the lives of village communities. We know for a fact that in this period, British rule over the Naga Hills district was characterized by a system of indirect rule, in which leading Naga figures took on administrative roles on behalf of the British administration. This raises the possibility that in some cases, administrators like Hutton may have bestowed far-reaching powers upon Naga associates they held in high esteem, perhaps sometimes to the extent that these powers resembled privileges of autonomous rulership.

Mittermaier’s statement about the relevance of dream interpretation to the framing of “symbolic debts, relationships, and meanings” (Mittermaier 2011, 2-3) provides perhaps the most useful model for the interpretation of the Sumi family’s oral accounts, though not all of them concerned dreams. Certainly, their accounts bear testimony to the fact that British colonial rule over the Nagaland region was not a straightforward matter but required constant negotiation with indigenous concepts of cultural and social hierarchy. Therefore, it is a futile endeavour to search for an answer to the question of whether British or Sumi Naga hierarchies ultimately prevailed in Hutton’s interactions with Vikhepu. Perhaps more aptly, we can regard the accounts of Vikhepu’s descendants as a testimony to the complex workings of the British colonial administration, which did not seek to abolish indigenous hierarchies and substitute them with societal structures imported from the West, but rather to work with these hierarchies and employ them as a tool to achieve administrative aims. Thus, we can argue that both British colonial sources and the family’s oral accounts are correct, as they reflect two different opinions about social hierarchies arrived at from

different cultural vantage points: for the British, Vikhepu and other Nagas were quite simply subordinates of the colonial administration, notwithstanding their social status in Naga society. For the Nagas, on the other hand, the actions of the colonial administration certainly had some influence on their lives, yet British notions of social hierarchy were something that remained abstract, superficial, and ultimately of little relevance to village communities, where traditional structures of social order remained much more tangible and relevant to daily lives than the power structures superimposed by the administration.

Conclusion

What, then, can we conclude from the oral accounts of the family? From an ethnomusicological perspective, they demonstrate the powerful effects that reconnecting cultural heritage communities with historical sound recordings can have, as illustrated by the emotional responses of Qheniho and Heshevi. Although we had never met before, they shared with me personal anecdotes about one of their ancestors in an informal manner after listening to Hutton's recordings, inspired by the mental associations the recordings had evoked in their minds. In this sense, their oral accounts illustrate that the domain of Naga oral tradition, including their performing arts, is deeply connected to the domain of Naga oral history, as both inform each other and contribute to shaping the collective memory of communities on their past.

Furthermore, we can recapitulate that Hutton's publications continue to inform the family's understanding of their genealogy, the history of their village, and Sumi culture, together with orally transmitted accounts about the connections of their ancestors to the British colonial administration. In this dual mode of knowledge production through written and oral sources, Hutton's publications play an important role. Arguably, his favourable representations of Vikhepu contributed to the family's perception that Vikhepu was perhaps the most important historical figure among their ancestors, which promoted the uninterrupted intergenerational transmission of their oral accounts of the two men's interactions through acts of narration, listening, and re-narration till the present day. This, in turn, illustrates how British colonial publications continue to inform not only the self-perception but also the discursive modes of Naga communities till today.

At this point, it is hard to assess the consequences of my fieldwork in Surumi with Hutton's recordings, which constituted an external intervention in these forms of knowledge production that have taken place in the family over generations. Will Hutton's recording of Vikhepu's voice become another stone in the mosaic of the family's collective memory of their ancestry, increasing Vikhepu's significance in their eyes even further? In the coming months, I will deposit the video recordings of my fieldwork with Hutton's cylinder recordings at the Archives and Research Center for Ethnomusicology in Gurgaon, as permanent archival documentation of the project outcomes. In this way, the video recordings of the family's oral accounts will become accessible to the wider public and remain preserved for future generations, as an archival resource offering a counter-perspective to the racially biased representations of Naga interpreters that proliferated in the Western world during the colonial period. In this sense, I hope that my documentation of the family's perspectives on the two men's interactions will become useful as a resource for further research on the complex social and cultural dynamics that shaped the encounters of the British with the Nagas.

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The Implementation of *Awiq-Awiq* for the Protection of a Forest in Highland Kakong, Lombok Indonesia

JOP KOOPMAN

This article focuses on local legislature stemming from customary practices installed by the local government of the *dusun* (hamlet) Kakong in the highlands of the *kecamatan* (district) Gangga on the island of Lombok in Indonesia to protect a lush forest surrounding a water spring. This water source is responsible for the distribution of drinking, washing, and farming water in three *desa* (municipalities), indirectly providing water for thousands of people. The legislature, or in other words, *awiq-awiq*, entails that if someone cuts down a tree in the protected forest, they have to replant 100 trees as punishment. I argue that the installation of this local type of legislature has transformed the perception of the inhabitants of Kakong concerning sustainability, biodiversity, climate change, and weather variability. Examples of adaptation processes and lively discussions about anthropogenic change are manifold in Kakong, as the effect of such change is highly present, materializing in a higher rate of precipitation, the entry of new pests such as the white fly, failed yields, and shifting temperatures. Effective leadership at the *dusun* level, in combination with the initiation of a new political role in the village (pekasih [canal manager]) for the empowerment of the *awiq-awiq* and *adat*, supports the adaptation and conservation effort area in Kakong. Based on qualitative data collected in 2022, I argue that local leadership and customary legislature and practices positively support adaptation and conservation processes in the highlands of Kakong, Lombok.

Keywords: Highlands, Lombok Indonesia, *Awiq-awiq*, Environmental Protection, Climate Change, Politics

We heard chainsaws in the distance coming from the protected forests surrounding the water spring. Everyone in the village was directly alerted and started running towards the mountain where the lush, protected forests are growing. After a while of searching, we found the perpetrator and dragged him and his chainsaw down the hill into the village. He told us that he was new in this area and simply did not know the forest was protected. Although this might be true, the rules are the rules. We broke his chainsaw with hammers, and he was prohibited from entering the forest ever again after he of course replanted the 100 trees to make amends for the one tree he had cut down.

This story was something that I experienced first-hand during one of my visits to the village of Kakong (*desa* Bentek) in Gangga, Lombok Utara, as I researched the protected forest and smallholder farmers' perceptions of climate change. In one reaction it reveals action – people running towards the sound of chainsaws – and a pragmatic reaction: protect the forest to protect our future water supply. In times of contemporary climate change and ever-changing weather patterns, the locals in Kakong understand why their future water supply is so important. The story also introduces a third agent: the community – 'we' broke his chainsaw, and 'we' heard the sounds in the distance. During this event it became clear who had to deal with the consequences if the protected forest was to be destroyed: the local community.

Such stories of localized responses for the preservation of nature are emerging from locations around the globe, although not every response is evenly successful in doing so. According to Maxton-Lee (2018), Indonesian deforestation persists and conservation in the archipelago mostly fails due to mixed messages from the policy level to the 'intent and wish' of the local communities for urban development. While many communities do see that deforestation is highly dangerous for their livelihoods, the rate of deforestation in Indonesia is higher than anywhere else in the world (Maxton-Lee 2018). This deforestation directly contributes to anthropogenic climate change, more frequently occurring landslides and the loss of habitat for endangered species of animals (Austin et al. 2019; Indarto, Kaneko, and Kawata 2015; Miyamoto 2020).

One of the largest contributors to this environmental change is agricultural development (Maxton-Lee 2018; Barraclough and Ghimire 1995; Krishna, Kubitz, Pascual & Qaim 2017). Also, in the case of Kakong, Gangga, one of the major contributors to deforestation before the instalment of the *awiq-awiq* was agriculture and forestry. The newly migrated groups of people from other parts of the island founded the village of Kakong and utilized the forests surrounding their newly built village (personal communication with the village leader, August 2023).

The water spring in Kakong is a source of water for approximately 6,000 people in the area because not only the village of Kakong but also the *desa* Genggeling and Gondang are using the water for farming, drinking, and washing. Hundreds of years ago, the three *desa* (municipalities) agreed to work together to protect the forest surrounding the water spring to continually support all the people with clean water (conversation with village elders, 22 June 2022). However, before the local legislature *awiq awiq* was installed in 2010, the forest was approximately 135 hectares large. After 2010, the protected area was around 35 hectares large and has remained at that size. The loss of territory of the forest raised calls from other officials, elders, and locals in the *desa* Genggeling and Gondang. They called the people of Kakong out for not taking care of the protected area well enough, which they were tasked to do. Consequently, the villagers in Kakong instigated an *awiq-awiq* to uphold their promise to their downland neighbours.

Awiq-awiq, which will be defined more thoroughly in the next paragraph, is a system of customary *adat* laws. *Adat* can be defined as a set of local customs, traditions, and laws that are different from the rules imposed by central governmental institutions. *Adat* existed before Dutch colonization and the forming of the Indonesian central state, and it differs across islands and cultures.

Before continuing with this paper, it is important to define the term *highlands* or at least, the definition that I am following in this paper. Highlands are upland regions having intricate relationships with their downland regions, although being a regions with unique characteristics taken from their geographical location. However, this is often a term that people from lowland regions impose upon highland peoples. Maybe, in local epistemologies, people in those highland areas do not define themselves as being highlanders and groups that are in a lower geographical location do define themselves as such.

In the case of Kakong, local epistemologies and vocabulary from communities on a lower geographical position describe the people of Kakong as *yang di atas* (those from high-up) and the people of Kakong describe the lower laying communities as *yang di bawah* (those from below). Meaning, the people of Kakong, while living 800 metres above sea level, view themselves as upland people. However, there are cases of surrounding villages on the same level of altitude where the people do not necessarily view themselves

as upland. Because the people of Kakong need to protect a forest and its water source for the area below, they constantly need to define and redefine what it means to live in an upland region while navigating the wants and needs of every stakeholder and agreements made with the people from below.

At the time of writing, there are still 30 protected forests (*hutan adat*) in Lombok, of which 29 are in North Lombok and one in East Lombok (Bae et al. 2014). In these forests community-based management has continued, having been passed down through generations, albeit for forest conservation, household needs, economic benefits, and cultural and religious practices. In conclusion, much of the exploitation of these protected forests was at a subsistence level.

In this paper, I argue that due to local legislature, the remaining forest is well-protected in terms of biodiversity, forest reclamation efforts, and conservation since the *awiq-awiq* was installed in 2010. I gathered data during my entry in the field in the first half of 2022 when I conducted participant observation among farmers, joined meetings specifically held for the protection of the forest, and met with locals, governmental institutions, and people from the surrounding *desa* to write down oral histories.

Exploring Kakong and Bentek

Dusun Kakong is located in *Desa* Bentek in the regency of Lombok Utara in the province of Nusa Tenggara Barat (NTB), Indonesia. The name of Bentek stems from *makam bebekeq*, which translates to the *bebekeq* tomb, which locates in the middle of the protected forest area. The protected forest is as high as 800 metres above sea level, while the community is located at 600 metres above sea level. In Figures 1 and 2, *Desa* Bentek and *dusun* Kakong are specified on the map.

Figure 1: *Desa* Bentek (taken from Google Maps)

In terms of local epistemologies, this area is defined as a highland region and is characterized by intricate upland-downland and upstream-downstream politics. These politics pertain to ownership of the protected forest, the water spring it provides, and the irrigation water that comes from said water spring. The lowland and upland communities have monthly communication about water supply in normal conditions, but when there is a case of prolonged drought, the village leaders gather once a week.

Figure 2: Kakong (taken from Google Maps)

Figure 3: Protected Forest in the distance and agricultural lands in the front (photo by author)

In Figure 3, the protected forest is depicted with a fertile valley underneath, through which the irrigation- and river system from the water spring flows. In Kakong, farmers generally have coffee, cacao, durian, coconut, and banana plantations. They combine this with peanut- and rice farming on the plateau beneath the protected forest area. The area is furthermore characterized by being the home of a multitude of people from various religious backgrounds, which is noteworthy since most of the people on Lombok are Muslim. In Bentek, Hindus and Buddhists are living in Seelos, and Muslims in Kakong. These various religious groups all come together to give protection to the forest, honour its connected rituals and ceremonies, and all have a say in how the forest is to be governed through local government-appointed groups.

Defining *awiq-awiq*

Awiq-awiq is rooted in a pre-existing conceptual order known as *sawen* (boundary delineation) and stems from local Sasak culture. According to *sawen*, the forest is regarded as ‘the mother’ since it was regarded as the source of water. If the forest was disturbed, the entire ecosystem would be affected by the hydrological system, eventually highly influencing the farmlands and the ocean. This human ecosystem concept provided the rationale for integrated resource management in the region.

Each section of the *sawen* had its own management position called a *mangku*. The forest was managed by the *mangku alas*, the *mangku bumi* managed agricultural land, and the *mangku laut* was responsible for the ocean and fishery. These leaders issued *awiq-awiq* when they observed that their responsible field was under pressure. They had several tasks such as survey and observation of their fields, visual mapping and boundary marking, and opening for fishing, harvesting, foraging, and extraction (Satria and Adhuri 2010; Bayo, Santoso, and Samadhi 2018). When a particular field was closed, the *mangku* appointed guards who voluntarily participated through *gotong royong*.¹

Although these political positions are currently waning due to the influence of national politics and religion, a revival of *awiq-awiq* has been observed in recent years (Satria and Adhuri 2010; Bae et al. 2014). A recent *awiq-awiq* that has been installed by the regions Tanjung and Pemenang is, for example, the prohibiting of blast fishing and the use of poisons while fishing. This *awiq-awiq* was even installed before the national ban in 2004 and is still upheld to this day. If fishers continued to use poison and bombs, their boats and gear would be burned by local fishers as retribution. During the recent earthquakes of 2018, an *awiq-awiq* was issued by local leadership against illegal forestry, whereby locals should replant the trees they cut down with new trees. The locals did this to not destroy the natural environment out of fear of more earthquakes and for the protection of the water supply. Local ontologies entail that the natural environment is protected by spirits, and when these spirits are disturbed, they can instigate natural hazards as an answer to environmental destruction.

Other forms of environmental protection stemming from *adat* have been observed throughout Indonesia, for example, *sasi* in Maluku, the work of local *adat* communities in Sulawesi, Kalimantan, Sumatra, and so on (Santika et al. 2017; Humaedi 2014). From this, we learn that in various locations in Indonesia, similar legislations stemming from *adat* are in place to protect forests, to foster a supply of water and food for the local community. However, *awiq-awiq* is not only to protect the environment but is in general local legislation. The local legislature can also be installed for the prohibition of child marriages (Siti et al. 2022) and plastic waste management (author’s own accounts).

Implementation in Kakong, Gangga and government support

While the *awiq-awiq* has existed for hundreds of years in the Kakong area, the legislation has strongly been enforced only since 2010. The locals from Kakong and the *desa* in the downland areas of the mountain

1. *Gotong royong* translates to mutual help and communal service.

range were concerned by the fact that already 100 hectares of the originally 135 hectares of protected forest had been lost due to forestry and agriculture. In Kakong, most of the farmers cultivate cacao, coffee, fruit-bearing trees, and coconuts, while the cultivation of rice and peanuts is decreasing because of anthropogenic climate change, influencing weather conditions in the region.

During conversations about the protected forest, most locals I interacted with pointed out that parts of the forest have different functions. There is the protected forest of 35 hectares that no one can enter without permission and, bordering on the protected forest, an agricultural production forest that expands to a few mountain tops in the neighbourhood where different crops are cultivated. These production forests also have land certification, making it difficult for local politicians to create legislation about how the farmers should cultivate their lands.

You can see the protected forest from here, that lush forest on the mountain stretching all the way to the river. The forest on this side of the river is tended to by us, the people of Kakong, and the forest on the other side is tended by the people of Genggelang. What about the forest on those mountains? I asked, pointing to the mountains close to the Kakong village (question by the author). Those are production forests, earlier they were protected too, but as more and more people moved here and sought means of living, they started to cultivate it. That is why the awiq-awiq is so strong now.

Interview with Adi, Kakong village on the 24th of June 2022 [translated from Sasak]

The *awiq-awiq* in Kakong entails that if someone enters the protected forest without permission of the *kepala dusun*² or the *kelompok adat*³ and cuts down a tree, they have to replant 100 new trees of the same species in the forest. Since 2010, three people have been caught red-handed, after which they had to replant trees at the places where they had destroyed the forest. After offenders are caught, their chainsaws are destroyed and a large mob of angry locals usually gather at their house to protest. This can be quite a daunting experience, but the locals do so to scare away other perpetrators from the forest and protected territory in the future.

Over the last few years, the Ministry of Forestry of the province of West Nusa Tenggara Barat (NTB) has also been involved in forest protection. It supports the locals in their protection efforts with funds, knowledge, and official legislature, making the forest even better protected than before. Currently, the province is helping the creation of a large *kelompok hutan* (forest management group), requiring every *dusun* surrounding the protected forest to create a *kelompok hutan* designated for the protection of the forest that meets once per week to discuss matters related to the protected area. After that, once per month representatives of all the *kelompok hutan* gather and discuss matters with representatives from the regency and the province to provide politically grounded support. While there is no KPH (Forest Management Unit) (Bae et al. 2014) present yet, because of local endeavours to get this forest officially protected there are plans to create such a KPH in the future to support local means of forest management.

Discontent from other stakeholders

Other stakeholders in the region, such as in the neighbouring *desa* Genggelang and Gondang, express discontent about the way the people of Kakong protect the forest area. Before the founding of Kakong village, the forest was around 135 hectares and shrank to 35 hectares due to human activity in the area, as previously mentioned. One of my collaborators, Supardi, told me this:

This can become a source of conflict when the people of Kakong do not take their task of protecting the forest seriously because it is also our lifeline of water which is used for crops, drinking, washing, and whatnot. I often

2. Hamlet head.

3. Village elders and important village figures deciding upon customary laws.

go to the leaders of Kakong and the desa, but they are not responding quickly enough to the impending dangers of illegal logging. Can you imagine, in the time of my grandmother there were still 135 hectares? Now all that is left is 35 hectares. Even though they are planning to utilize the water spring for tourism... It is unheard of! Do they have awiq-awiq now? Good. Only 30 years too late in my honest opinion.

-Interview with a political leader in Genggelang on the 2nd of June, 2022 [translated from Sasak]

In the quote above, one of the people of the downland villages is voicing their discontent about the present situation in and surrounding the forest. As the topic of the protected forest is particularly sensitive because it provides a viable water source for over 6,000 people in the villages beneath, emotions are rising among people that are discontent about how the people in Kakong take care of the forest.

Conflict can arise when different stakeholders in forest management have different goals (Niemelä et al. 2005; Fisher 1999; Riggs et al. 2016; Krishna et al. 2017), as all stakeholders have different goals and ideas about how to preserve the forest as well as they can. Besides that, conflicting interests between *desa*, locals, and the government have been present about illegal land tenure and land certification whereby parts of the already lost territory of the protected forest (c. 100 ha) had been given illegal certification and were resold to others. As Riggs et al. (2016) argued, land tenure and certification conflicts in Indonesia are very hard to solve.

Another conflict surrounding the protected forest is its water supply. Water conflicts often arise from misunderstandings between upstream and downstream communities pertaining to ownership and rights (Astawa 2004). These conflicts pertain to property rights concerning water storage, division, and disposal. Astawa (2004) argues, in his conference paper on communities in the Rinjani National Park, Lombok, that the majority of communities experience water conflicts between upland and downland areas. The case of upland Kakong and downland Genggelang and Gondang mirrors this conflict.

Although the upheld customary *adat* laws surrounding the protected forest in Kakong also pertain to water management, institutional laws make it more complex. Part of this complexity lies in the fragmentation of laws concerning water use and preservation. Surface water is under the jurisdiction of Public Works, groundwater is the responsibility of the Department of Mining and Energy, and water conservation, specifically in upland regions, is governed by the Ministry of Forestry (Astawa 2004; Santika et al. 2017).

While being a problem that needs solving, the *kepala dusun* needs to take a key role in these matters to give resolution. The position of *kepala dusun* at the village level is very important as he can effectively mobilize its citizens and give voice to unheard and unseen stakeholders and redirect them to the larger stakeholders at play (Koopman 2021, 2022). Furthermore, he can function as a bridge between customary *adat* laws and institutional laws, by participating in the local government and the designated *adat* groups. While *adat* rules can sometimes be a bit cryptic for laypeople, the *kepala dusun* can translate them effectively.

In the case of Kakong, the *kepala dusun* was the person that instigated the strong *awiq-awiq* in 2010 to ensure a future water supply and enough forest to support that source. Although very valid concerns, due to the strong local legislature that has been installed and close partnership with the Ministry of Forestry these problems will be resolved in the near future, as collective action and cooperation are needed to maintain this lush and protected area.

Increased perception of anthropogenic change

Perception research on localized responses to forestry is necessary because protecting a forest from various factors and dangers potentially influences the way locals think and perceive anthropogenic change. To incorporate perception theory in this paper I have included four overlapping axioms which need to be explained to paint an all-encompassing picture: how people perceive forestry through cultural lenses (perception); how people comprehend what they see based on their cultural models and social locations (knowledge); how they give value to what they know in terms of shared meanings and memory (valuation);

and how they respond, individually and collectively, based on these values and meanings (response) (Roncoli, Crane & Orlove 2016).

In the case of Kakong, villagers display all four axioms of perception in terms of forestry and anthropogenic change. The board of elders from Kakong told me the following:

We need to protect the forests because through the ages we have already done that. The water spring in the middle of the forest is like a lifeline, without it, we could not do agriculture nor wash or live in this place. I think if we allowed the diminishing of the forests to continue that we had to migrate away because life would simply not be possible without it. We can already feel the area becoming drier and weather variabilities have been rising lately. Because previous generations from other desa and this village have tried to protect it, we see it as our duty to continue that tradition. Hence the reason that every year we give thanks to God through a ritual, called Menunas-Memule, for the cleansing of the water and the forest before the planting season. Once per five to ten years, we make a sacrifice to appease our God and to show that we are still taking care of our water spring and its forests. This ritual is called Sedeqah Gumi Paer Bebekeq. Besides that, it is our duty to protect this lifeline for the next generations and the people living in the lower parts of this area, they are all dependent on this forest and its water.

-Interview with a village elder in Kakong, 12th of June 2022 [translated from Sasak]

In this quote, all four of the previously described axioms of perception theory are effectively described:

(1), Perception can be effectively described as perceiving the world through our senses. In the quote above, my collaborator says: *We can already feel the area becoming drier and weather variabilities have been rising lately.* This shows that locals are already effectively thinking about the changes that happened and the changes to come.

(2), Knowledge, in local Indonesian epistemologies, is understood as closely related to experience (Roncoli, Crane & Orlove 2016; Larsen et al. 2012). What people ‘know’ about anthropogenic change is as much a reflection of their beliefs, values, worldviews, and objectives as a descriptive account of what anthropogenic change is and what they must do about it (Weber 2006). In the quote above, my collaborators say the following: *Because previous generations from other desa and this village have tried to protect it, we see it as our plight to continue that tradition.* They have learned the practice of protecting the forests from their elders and others in the region. Elders are vested with knowledge because they have accumulated past experiences, including climate events, impacts, and changes (Barnhardt and Oscar Kawagley 2005). Since local knowledge is often passed down by elders to their children, cultural, collective, and social memory play a huge role in giving shape to knowledge systems.

(3) Valuation, people’s perceptions and knowledge systems are framed by cultural contexts with which they ascribe meaning and value to what they see and know (Roncoli, Crane & Orlove 2016). Shared meanings and sense-making of memory are tightly connected to the axiom of knowledge. The locals of Kakong have received a lot of knowledge from the elders and generations passed, and they value that knowledge highly. Take, for example, the ritual that is being held every year: *hence the reason that every year we give thanks to God through a ritual cleansing the water and the forest before the planting season.* The *pekasih*⁴ confessed to me that there was a time in recent history when they stopped this ritual, however, in the years after that crops started to fail, the forest shrank, and the water was not as pure as it normally was. They reinstated the ritual soon after, as they did not want to anger God. The ritual might have given an extra incentive to the people of Kakong to care for their environment through a divine practice such as a ritual.

(4) Response, is captured in this part of the quote above: *Besides that, it is our duty to protect this lifeline for the next generations and the people living in lower parts of this area, they are all dependent on this forest and its water.* Understanding the interactions of culture and climate, and in particular, the role of perceptions,

4. A position elected democratically. The *pekasih* is responsible for even water distribution in times of droughts. *Pekasih* literally translates to ‘canal manager’ and is unique to Lombok, as it stems from *adat*.

knowledge, and values as elements of these interactions, brings us to focus on adaptive responses (Roncoli, Crane & Orlove 2016). Adaptive responses to mitigate the effects of anthropogenic change on the water quality and the protected forests are threefold in Kakong. Firstly, the newly created role of *pekasih* in the village supports the control of water in the region. If there are prolonged droughts, he creates a schedule for the villages and farmers that need water, in order to provide everyone equally in their needs. He is also responsible for the management of irrigation lanes in terms of maintenance. Secondly, *awiq-awiq* prohibits any people to cut down trees or to enter the protected forest without permission. Lastly, the people in Kakong take active measures to ensure a viable future for the forest via government support and tourism activities surrounding the water spring, enabling them to gather the funds for the management of the forest.

Heightened perception of anthropogenic change in plantation farming

Another factor that contributes to an enhanced perception of anthropogenic change among the people of Kakong is the increase of invasive and climate-related pests in the region. In the following quote, one of my interlocutors is describing the entry of the white fly (*Bemisia tabaci*):

Because of the weather conditions the last few years those white flies have become a real pest. They have multiplied so much, that if you would run around in the morning in a black shirt it would be white in a few minutes. The white fly causes all the leaves of our coffee, cacao, durian, and other fruits to turn black. Because of this, our harvests fail and even in some cases, the fruit-bearing trees die.

-interview with a farmer in Kakong, 4th of May 2022 [translated from Sasak]

According to Kriticos et al. (2020) and Aregbesola et al. (2019), white fly pests are a direct consequence of a warming but also wetter climate which makes the area more suitable for the insects to flourish and reproduce. These pests, as shown above, directly influence the yield the farmers can harvest from their orchards. Additionally, the white fly also has been seen to affect horticulture in the area whereby, due to the influence of rapidly changing weather conditions, the white fly wreaks havoc with viruses and bacterial diseases among tomato and chilli plantations, causing harvests to fail.

It is not only the production forests bordering the village of Kakong and the protected forest area that is affected by anthropogenic change. The areas below the protected forest area that can normally be harvested up to five times with a variety of rice and peanuts are heavily influenced by on the one hand wet conditions during the peanut season and on the other hand pests and viruses during the rice season. Normally there are no such problems in the highland area of Kakong, as water is abundant due to the protected forest, and because of its elevated geographic location pests such as the white fly and other insects do not thrive in its climate. Local farmers have sought to adjust to these new realities through means of a combination of pesticides and traditional techniques such as the use of cross-planting species that keep these flies at a distance.

As described above, locals in Kakong are reliant on the protected forest for the viability of their livelihoods, and they are also invested in the area for spiritual guidance and guardianship.

Spiritual guardianship

Astawa (2004) argues that “the ecological and sacred functions are no longer important to people in Lombok. On the contrary, people are more interested in the economic value of forests”. There is indeed a rise in economic interest in forested areas, however, arguing that the ecological and sacred functions are no longer important to people in Lombok is overgeneralizing at best. While there is a decline in Indonesia of spiritual activity connected to forests, it has not vanished nor become less important in local Sasak epistemologies (Libasut

Figure 4: *Purba lian* tree, regarded as *istana* (anchor) and dimensional gateway by locals (photo by author)

2016; Telle 2009; Rahayu et al. 2021). In the case of Kakong, the yearly and five-yearly rituals are a striking example of spiritual activity and guardianship pertaining to the forest.

Local epistemologies also explain that there are several anchors – or *istana* (palace[s]) in the local language – located in the forest where spirits live, see Figure 4 for such an anchor. An anchor can be defined as a physical (often natural) object such as a rock, tree, waterfall, or river that functions as a gateway between the dimensional plane of spirits and ours. These spirits are believed to be governed by *Dewi Anjani*, the spirit queen (Smith 2021), who resides on the top of the volcano Rinjani. People from the upland regions of Gangga, and in general throughout Lombok (while becoming less in urbanized centres),

have intricate relationships with magic, the spirit world, and a system of ancestry that can influence day-to-day life. Furthermore, they have a relationship with the presence of multiple *makam*, or holy gravesites, in the forest where members of the local community and people from outside the region pray, meditate, and visit to honour their ancestors.

These gravesites are often surrounded by very large *Purba lian* trees (see Figure 4) which are viewed as *istana*, or anchors that are a gateway between our dimension and the other. Locals call that other dimension *alam ghaib* – the closest English translation would be the ‘the other world,’ as *alam* translates to ‘nature’ and *ghaib* to ‘unseen’ in *Bahasa Indonesia*, the official and national language of Indonesia. It is thereby a different dimensional plane where beings live that is, according to local beliefs, interconnected with ours. The term *alam ghaib* stems from the Arabic expression *al-ghaib* and translates to ‘the unseen’. However, the local notion of *alam ghaib* is also heavily influenced by pre-Islam animism, Hinduism, and Buddhism, thus creating a syncretic belief system.

Regarding the protected forest, the locals believe that if the forest is taken care of, the spirits, or in local terms *jinn*, living there will support their battle against new pests introduced by anthropogenic change. They believe that the spirit world is thoroughly connected with our plane of existence and can influence events in this world. For that reason, the anchored palaces need to be treated with the utmost respect. If not, it will cause adversity for the local community. When one enters the forest, they will be greeted by the sound of many types of birds, see a lot of tracks of mammals and reptiles, and be enveloped in a lush green forest. The locals believe that the animals living there are owned by the *jinn*. For this reason, the locals will not bother them, which thereby contributes to the health and prosperity of the forest.

Conclusion

This paper addressed the question of how the local legislature and *adat* practices are instigated by the local community to protect a lush forest area of 35 hectares surrounding a water spring which is the primary water source for over 6,000 people in the *desa* Genggelang, Gondang and *dusun* Kakong. Furthermore, this paper sought to explore how these protective practices improved the perceptions of anthropogenic change of the locals in Kakong.

The forest surrounding the water spring in Kakong Village Lombok is protected by the local practice of *awiq-awiq*, a type of legislature that is instigated by the local community themselves rather than the government. By instigating this practice, it is forbidden to enter the forest without permission and to cut down trees. If caught, perpetrators need to pay a hefty fine or need to replant 100 trees per tree that was cut down.

In history, the forest was protected by the *desa* Genggelang and Gondang, but since the people of Kakong migrated to the place where they are living now, they are taking care of the water spring and forest. This causes political and social tensions to arise, because before the people of Kakong migrated there the forest was 135 hectares large, while now, due to the construction of a settlement, the forest is 35 hectares large.

After the *kepala dusun* of Kakong noticed the decline of the forest, he tightened the rules surrounding the *awiq-awiq* and strengthened relations with the Ministry of Forestry of the central government to make sure the forest would not decline further. Besides that, he created multiple groups and positions that have the responsibility for water control, the condition of the forest, and the rules of *adat* to support the *awiq-awiq*.

The tightened form of *awiq-awiq* caused the people of Kakong to actively think about the effects of anthropogenic change and the role we humans play in that change. Examples are given of people actively talking and able to perceive climate and anthropogenic change in their surrounding environment. Local epistemologies about the otherworld and spirits promote the safety of the forest and its biodiversity, resulting in yearly and five-yearly rituals celebrating the water spring, the fertility of the land, and the condition of the forest.

In conclusion, although the area of protected forest used to be larger, since 2010 strongly enforced *awiq-awiq* in the forest has halted its decline and has given it a protected status through a localized type of

legislature combined with the support of the central government. With local epistemologies concerning the spiritual guardianship over the forest combined with government support and pressure from reliant downland and downstream villages, the forest is currently preserved and there is optimism for its future.

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The health consequences of urbanization in Nepal: perspectives from a participatory photo project with recent rural-urban migrants

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What new challenges to health do recent rural-to-urban migrants in Nepal face? How do newly urbanized individuals navigate and seek healthcare in the city? This photo essay offers a glimpse of the answers to these questions from the perspective of newly urbanized people living in Kirtipur and Pokhara, two rapidly growing urban areas in Nepal. It draws on a nine-month participatory study which used participatory photography, amongst other methods, to better understand the health opportunities and risks faced by new rural-urban migrants. All photographs presented in this essay were taken and selected by research participants and are accompanied by their narrations of what these images represent to them. Consequently, this essay provides insights into how the newly urbanized themselves understand threats to their health, and how they understand the urban health system they are confronted with as service users.

Keywords: Rural-urban migration; health seeking behaviour; health services; participatory photography; Nepal

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Introduction

As is the case in many low- and middle-income countries, urbanization is taking place rapidly in Nepal. The 2021 census found that the percentage of the population living in urban areas now stands at 66.8%, compared to 63.2% a decade earlier. This trend looks set to continue, with Nepal expected to be the second fastest urbanizing country in the world between 2018-2050, with a projected annual urbanization rate of 2% (UN DESA 2018, 52). High rates of urban growth are particularly apparent in the Kathmandu Valley, but also in other rapidly expanding urban areas, including the Pokhara Valley, and in market and border towns in the Terai southern lowlands (Bakrania 2015).

Moving from a rural village to the city is often seen as offering a variety of new economic, social, and educational opportunities. But as is true across the world, it also poses new health risks. These include non-communicable diseases resulting from lifestyle and environmental changes (Hernandez et al. 2012; Misha and Ganda 2007) and psychological stressors (Mucci et al. 2020), as well as communicable diseases caused by increasing population density, precarious and health-harming working conditions and sub-standard accommodation, often in informal settlements with inadequate basic amenities (Alirol et al. 2011; Awoh and Plugge 2016; Boadi et al. 2005; Pardhi et al. 2020).

Moving from a rural to an urban area also affects the ability of individuals to access healthcare services (Else et al. 2019). In theory, healthcare options available to urban residents far surpass what is provided in villages in both quantity and quality. Yet here too there are challenges, and in practice, newly urbanized individuals often have limited access to quality health care in Nepal: they can find it difficult to navigate the vastly more complex pluralistic urban health systems (Else et al. 2019; Ezeh et al. 2017). In Nepal, as in most of the world, the newly urbanized are not treated in health policy and planning as a specific population group with particular needs. Yet this combination of new health risks and challenges in accessing health services, we argue, means that they need to be considered as such.

To contribute towards the visibilization of the specific health needs of recent rural-urban migrants, this study sought to offer a deeper understanding of their own perceptions, experiences, and health seeking behaviours.

Methods

The photographs and narrations presented here are part of a larger multi-method participatory study involving people who have recently moved from rural areas of Nepal to Kirtipur (in the Kathmandu Valley) and Pokhara, two rapidly growing urban areas.

Participatory photography, often called *photovoice* (Wang and Burris 1997), has been widely utilised by researchers in a variety of fields, including in health research. It was a particularly appropriate methodological approach for this study for two key reasons. Firstly, as a means of data collection, it allowed participants to both reflect over time on the project's research questions, and then to utilise the photographs they had taken as a prompt for reflecting on and comparing their perceptions and experiences, and sharing that knowledge and understanding with the research team in a way that resulted in a richness of detail and understanding that non-visual methods, such as interviewing, may not have produced (Cooper and Yarbrough 2010). Secondly, as a means of communicating the concerns of this particular section of the

community (Sutton-Brown 2014), the photographs allowed for the effective communication of their concerns to wider audiences, including health service providers and planners, and readers of this article (Budig et al. 2018).

For the participatory photo project reported here, three newly urbanized persons were recruited in Pokhara and three in Kirtipur – part of a larger cohort of participants in the wider research project. The selection criteria were designed to ensure that there was a gender balance, and also that the groups represented different types of migrants (i.e., individuals who had moved to the city for a variety of reasons). Five of the participants had moved directly from a rural village to an urban area within the last five years, and one had originally migrated to a semi-urban area as an intermediate step before eventually making his way to live in Kirtipur to pursue his studies. Although all participants were offered anonymity (see details of ethical approval below), they all chose to have their names associated with the pictures and narrations presented in this article, which they saw as an important way of drawing attention to the health challenges that they believe they face.

Participants were introduced to the project's aims and participatory photography as a method during a one-day workshop. They were then asked to work in their group of three over two days, walking around their local area and photographically documenting their own views and experiences in relation to the following research questions (RQs):

- 1) What new challenges to your health have you encountered since you moved to the city?
- 2) Where do/would you go if you had a health problem?

The group then selected the photographs that they felt best represented their views and experiences in relation to these two RQs. The participants and the researchers discussed the selected photographs in a focus group setting. The commentary that follows each photograph is taken from the transcripts of those discussions, translated into English.

The project received ethical approval from the Nepal Health Research Council (Ref. 173/2020) and from the University of Sheffield Ethical Review Committee (Ref. 034081).

The first set of photographs focuses on the urban determinants of health (RQ1); the second on health services that the participants identified as being available for their potential use (RQ2). The fieldwork was carried out in January and February 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic (although at a time when COVID rates in Nepal had fallen to a relatively low level). As such, health issues were very much in the minds of the participants, and this was reflected in some of their comments and choices of photographs. Nevertheless, it was clear that the pandemic was only one of a wide range of health concerns they had.

New challenges to health since moving to the city

The health threats on which the participants focused were those directly arising from the urban environment. They frequently compared the environmental health problems they were aware of in the city to the situation in the rural areas where they previously lived. They were clear that the authorities should be doing more to reduce the health risks they faced.

Figure 1: 'Rubbish', Kirtipur (Credit: Ammalal Sejuwal, Khila Karki, and Vishan Thami)

“We took this photo to show the problem of rubbish in our surroundings. Rubbish is thrown everywhere haphazardly and has potentially serious effects on our health. This rubbish can cause many different diseases. The ward and municipal authorities should be doing proper waste management – and people shouldn’t be throwing their rubbish in the streets.”

Figure 2: 'Air pollution', Kirtipur (Credit: Ammalal Sejuwal, Khila Karki, Vishan Thami)

“We took this photo to show the smoke and dust in central Kirtipur. This is made worse by the number of vehicles and poorly maintained roads. This pollution can cause different types of disease and

can damage the lungs. The authorities should properly manage the roads to control the levels of dust and smoke in the city.”

Figure 3: ‘Roadside seller’, Pokhara (Credit: Ramu Thakuri, Shanti Bhandari, Tej Kumari Baral)

“After migrating from rural to urban areas, many people are involved in selling on the roadside for their livelihood. There is dust and dirt in the road which creates risks to their health, but they are compelled to work for a living. People suffer from different kinds of diseases due to this issue. The metropolitan city authorities should make plans and programs focusing on the poor people to protect them from dangerous working conditions.”

Figure 4: ‘Traffic’, Pokhara (Credit: Ramu Thakuri, Shanti Bhandari, Tej Kumari Baral)

“In Pokhara we have big problems of not obeying the traffic rules, of drivers with no knowledge of traffic rules, negligence while driving vehicles, driving vehicles without a driving licence, and crossing the road recklessly. This creates big risks of death or injury on the roads.”

Seeking healthcare in the city

The overcrowded nature of urban health services and the need to identify low-cost yet convenient sources of care were prominent themes in the participants’ discussions of where they go to get treatment. In both Kirtipur and Pokhara, expensive and high-quality private medical facilities are available but, as for many people in Nepal, the participants’ first stop is invariably a local private pharmacy or medical shop (where medical/specialized doctors provide their services; some even have diagnostic services and pharmacy) for relatively low-cost medicines and advice. But in some cases, participants identified the need to visit a government hospital – or one run by an NGO.

Figure 5: 'Private pharmacy', Kirtipur (Credit: Ammalal Sejuwal, Khila Karki, Vishan Thami)

“People are concerned about their health and are having health check-up in the pharmacy.”

Figure 6: ‘Pharmacy’, Pokhara (Credit: Ramu Thakuri, Shanti Bhandari, Tej Kumari Baral)

“This is the pharmacy at Gandaki Medical College¹ – people are packed together and standing in a queue. Despite coronavirus, there is a big crowd in this place. People come here to get health services, but at the same time the crowd means that they are risking their health.”

1. Gandaki Medical College is affiliated with Tribhuvan University. This pharmacy is thus unusual: in most urban areas, it would be more common for people to visit a privately-run pharmacy/medical shop as a first port-of-call for health problems.

Figure 7: ‘Queuing at an NGO-run hospital’², Kirtipur (Credit: Ammalal Sejuwal, Khila Karki, Vishan Thami)

“We took this photo to show people standing in a queue for health services, although here at least they are socially distanced. Inside the hospital, children are getting vaccinated or receiving treatment. We took this picture because it shows that people are being conscious about their health during the coronavirus pandemic.”

2. Kirtipur Hospital is run by phect-NEPAL – a not-for-profit NGO (phectnepal.org).

Figure 8: 'Fever Clinic', Pokhara (Credit: Ramu Thakuri, Shanti Bhandari, Tej Kumari Baral)

“This is a government hospital: Western Regional Hospital. The health services here are cheap, which is helpful for people with a low income. Lots of different services are available in this hospital. As the services here are cheaper [compared to private hospitals], people with low economic status can afford them. Coronavirus has spread all over the country now, and this hospital now provides special health services for coronavirus patients as well.”

Figure 9: ‘Private kidney hospital’, Pokhara (Credit: Ramu Thakuri, Shanti Bhandari, Tej Kumari Baral)

“Different specialized health services are available in Pokhara Metropolitan City. Services for heart, dental, kidney, eyes, nose, throat, ears, skin, etc. are available for those who can afford them. If treatment is not possible in these specialized hospitals, referral can be done and patients can be taken to other bigger hospitals by ambulance.”

Figure 10: ‘Advertisement for the National Health Insurance scheme’, Pokhara (Credit: Ramu Thakuri, Shanti Bhandari, Tej Kumari Baral)

“In order to meet the basic health needs of low-income people, there is now a government health insurance scheme, which is available in Pokhara metropolitan city. A total of 3,500 rupees has to be paid for a family of five. This gives free treatment up to 100,000 rupees for different disease conditions. This has been very helpful to low-income people.”

Discussion

What do these photographs, and the explanations provided by our participants, enable us to see? Here we briefly discuss the insights that the project provided on the two issues of interest in the study: how recent migrants understand the new health threats they face in the city; and where they seek care amongst the diverse and complex ecosystem of healthcare providers that are available in both Kirtipur and Pokhara.

Understanding new health threats

It was striking that participants focused on new environmental health threats: in particular, issues around pollution, waste management, and traffic. Certainly, these are amongst the most immediately apparent differences between city and village life, and participants showed an acute awareness of these threats to their health. At the same time, it was noticeable that these are all ‘external’ health threats. Other urbanization-related health challenges that frequently appear in the literature – for example changing diets, or increased usage of alcohol and tobacco – were not selected by our participants as issues to be documented or discussed. One reason may be that it is far easier to recognize (and thus feel threatened by) environmental rather than personal behavioural factors. Here we see a direct contrast with the oft-

critiqued tendency of government policy to focus on promoting behavioural change in response to health problems (for example, obesity).

As we described above, the fieldwork for this project took place during the COVID pandemic. While this was not photographed by participants as a new health threat in the city (by this point in the pandemic, COVID had been spreading widely in rural areas in Nepal as well as urban ones), they certainly identified its impact on people's behaviour and the risks they were taking when accessing health services (Figures 6 and 7), as well as the development of additional temporary health facilities (the Fever Clinic in Pokhara in Figure 8). Here we found participants intuitively linking our two research questions, looking not only at health threats, but about how those threats affected the use of, and availability of, health services in their local area.

Navigating the health system

Turning to the issue of navigating the local health system, the photographs and discussions of them revealed that participants had a sophisticated knowledge of their local health service ecosystem, understood as the range of providers available for different forms of health need in their locality. As is perhaps to be expected, there was variability in the depth of knowledge, but participants were all able to talk knowledgeably about a wide range of service providers in their respective localities including government-run facilities (Figure 8), private providers (Figures 5, 6 and 9), and those run by NGOs (Figure 7) or other bodies (Figure 6).

In both Kirtipur (Figure 5) and Pokhara (Figure 6), the local pharmacy was generally identified as the first place to visit for most non-emergency health needs – although participants also knew where more specialized treatment was available where required and were able to make informed decisions about the appropriate providers of care for a range of different health problems.

These perspectives of rural-urban migrants challenge how policymakers in Nepal (and elsewhere) generally think about the health system. The patchwork of healthcare options photographed and discussed by our participants did not match the neat organograms of government-run services through which health policymakers generally think and act. Although it is clear that they are widely used across the population, health policymakers and planners in Nepal rarely, for example, think of pharmacies as integral parts of the country's health system. Understanding how individuals experience the diverse urban healthcare ecosystem is necessary in order to be able to properly tailor service delivery to meet the needs of the newly urbanized.

Conclusion

Working alongside recently urbanized people themselves to understand issues of healthcare access and utilization can provide important insights for informing policy and planning in Nepal, and potentially elsewhere. The experiences of individual patients/users are often overlooked in health systems planning. But this is particularly true of those who have recently migrated from rural to urban areas, who are rarely, if ever, seen as a distinct population group in their own right, with their own needs and challenges. The types of participatory methods utilized in this study represent one way of more fully understanding the experiences and perceptions of recent migrants.

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Observation: Irfan's Ghost

CATRIONA CHILD

This essay records a series of events that occurred within my Kashmiri family shortly after I moved to India in 2005. Over the years, I had heard many stories of spirit possession from friends living in Himalayan states, but this was the first time I had the opportunity to observe the phenomenon at close quarters. The scenes described in the text took place in Delhi over several weeks in the winter of 2005–2006.

Keywords: Delhi, India, ghost, possession, Kashmir, adolescent

I am a British woman from a family with a long history in the sub-continent, so in some ways, it was unsurprising that I should end up living there. In June 2005, I married a Kashmiri called Tariq*, who runs a handicrafts business from an office and showroom in South Delhi, and moved to India permanently.

In December 2005, during the fog of a Delhi winter, Tariq's youngest brother, Irfan, came from Kashmir to stay with us. My husband's family is large, with eight children surviving to adulthood. While Tariq is the eldest, Irfan, then 16 years old, is the youngest. In 2005, Irfan was a classic adolescent boy: tall, gangly, with a shock of dark curly hair and a permanently surly expression. He mooched around the neighbourhood, hands sunk deep into jean pockets, and eyes fixed permanently on the ground. On Fridays, however, he would don a white kurta pyjama and go to the mosque to pray.

He and I had just one point of connection. As he was quite tech-savvy and I was trying to master the Photoshop program, I roped him in to help, which he did gladly.

One Saturday morning, Irfan and I were working on the computer in the office, which is separated from the showroom by a glass wall. Tariq called us to the apartment for lunch. Irfan went, but I was not hungry and stayed behind.

About an hour later, I heard voices and looked through the window into the showroom to see Tariq and Irfan on a sofa in deep conversation. Oddly, Irfan was looking Tariq straight in the eye, something he never did, except perhaps with his mother. Curious, I entered the showroom and found Tariq apparently interrogating his brother (I do not speak Kashmiri but understand a few words) and Irfan responding in a strange, deep voice unlike his own, all the while aggressively holding Tariq's gaze.

Tariq stopped the interrogation and called his brother Bashir, one of the more religious family members. The Koran was produced from the cupboard where it is carefully kept; Bashir handed it to Irfan and asked

*All names have been changed

him to read a passage. Shockingly, for a boy who prayed at the mosque every Friday, Irfan pushed the Holy Book away from him with considerable force.

When I finally caught Tariq alone and demanded an explanation, this is what I was told. In short, Irfan had been possessed by a ghost, and during the interrogation in the showroom, Tariq was speaking directly to the entity and not to Irfan. This, apparently, is what the ghost said.

He, the ghost, had been sitting under a tree in Kashmir with his family when Irfan, returning from a cricket match, stopped and urinated on him. Much annoyed, the ghost then attached itself to Irfan but did not manifest as long as the teenager was in Kashmir. However, the journey to Delhi was unsettling, and the entity began to show itself. Tariq had been alerted to the problem during lunch when Irfan greedily consumed the entire communal plate of rice, which should be shared among the family. Ghosts are hungry, it seems, and require feeding. Raised in Kashmir, where nearly every family has instances of possession, Tariq recognized the signs and brought Irfan down to the showroom to speak to him and the entity in a quiet place.

There was much discussion about what to do next. One of the more devout uncles was asked to bring a 'ghost catcher' from Nizamuddin (the settlement around the shrine of Delhi's most revered Sufi saint). The ghost catcher and the uncle arrived. I was told that the ghost catcher had a team of ghosts that could be unleashed like a pack of hounds to round up any unwanted beings. The 'team' checked the showroom, office, and apartment. We were told that the young boy who worked with us, Amir, also had a ghost, which waited for him in the street every morning and accompanied him to the showroom but did not enter the house.

Koranic text was written in yellow (possibly turmeric) on scraps of paper and stuck onto every door and window in the house and showroom. More text was written in ink on paper that was then torn into small pieces and placed in a jug of water, which was kept on a table in the living room.

We all returned to the house for the catcher to interview the ghost. He drew a two-inch square on a piece of paper with biro and filled it in with ink. He then invited Irfan to look at it. Later, Irfan told me that it was like looking at a television screen. He could see the entity on the screen looking back at him.

Tariq told me that the ghost catcher had explained that ghosts tend to attach to young, good-looking boys who have never touched alcohol. When we were all together in the living room, Tariq pointed at me and asked if I was ever likely to be attacked by a ghost. The catcher gave me a long, hard look and then said, 'No, never'. While relieved at the news, I was unsure what this said about my moral character.

Employing some technique that I did not see, the ghost catcher extracted the ghosts from Irfan and Amir, respectively, and tied them tightly with string. The uncle and ghost catcher then departed, apparently to dispose of the ghosts safely. Except that they did not quite. In a comic turn among all the drama, they forgot Amir's ghost and had to return to collect it.

It has to be said that Irfan was different after the ghost catcher's visit. Much of the time, he was back to his sulky, adolescent self, but every so often the ghost would return, and Irfan would twitch strangely and glare at whoever was speaking to him.

Each evening, there was a ritual with serious intent that was comic to watch. At 10 p.m., Bashir would take the jug of water containing the holy writings and spray each member of the family with it as we sat together in the living room. Now, Delhi winter nights can be chilly, and the apartment had no heating, so being sprinkled with cold water was extremely unpleasant. One family member, Ahmed, who was sceptical about the whole situation, used to become extremely irritable each time the cold-water performance was enacted.

On one of those evenings, we were all in the living room as usual. In those days, we had no chairs, and everyone sat on the floor, Kashmiri-style. I was right on the edge of the group, and Irfan was lying on the floor in the middle, close to Bashir. He began to twitch, and Bashir massaged his legs to soothe him. Wanting to stop the weirdness, which seemed to have gone on long enough, I said the Lord's Prayer in my head without moving a muscle. Irfan sat bolt upright, gave me one of his penetrating glares, and said, 'She's praying something'. For me, that was proof that I was not hallucinating.

Irfan's 'ghost attacks' gradually became less and less frequent. The last one I witnessed occurred one night when I was sitting on the end of his bed, talking about inconsequential things. He suddenly said, 'The ghost is coming', and a few seconds later, he became strange and restive for about half an hour before returning to normal.

It was decided that he must go back to Kashmir for 'treatment' by the family Sufi guru. The day they were due to drive to Anantnag, where the guru lived, Irfan got in the car. But it would not start. Rashid, the driver, tried and tried, but the engine would not fire despite the fact that it had started perfectly well earlier in the day. Eventually they got going and arrived safely in Anantnag.

Sometime after, Irfan told me that the guru, who knew him well, took him under his grey woollen *pheran*¹ and held him close. Irfan felt a powerful wave of heat coursing through his body before the guru released him and he returned home. After that, the ghost was gone for good. The only apparent consequence, which may not be connected at all, was that Bashir, who was deeply upset by the whole business, began to follow a 'guru' in Kashmir, not the family one, who, Tariq said, taught him 'wrong mantras'. Later, Bashir developed signs of mental illness and was eventually diagnosed with mild schizophrenia.

So, what did I make of it all? I kept meticulous notes throughout the event, which lasted for about a month. For me, the clincher was the 'Lord's Prayer' incident. There was no way Irfan could have known that I was praying, and I'm not openly religious at all. It did all happen. The part I doubt is that Amir ever had a ghost and that this was a ploy by the ghost catcher to charge the family more money.

Catriona Child is an environmentalist and editor with a particular interest in ethnoecology and the culture of the indigenous communities of northeast India. She is currently Acting Director of the Highland Institute, Kohima, and divides her time between her duties in Nagaland and her family in Delhi and Kashmir.

1. A *pheran* or *phiran* is the traditional outfit for both males and females in Kashmir. Usually made of wool, it has full sleeves and extends to the knees or below. Unlike a coat, the front opening extends only a short way below the neck.

Conference Report: Southeast Asian Frontier #1: Highlands, 18-20 August 2022, Yogyakarta, Indonesia, and Remote

SINDHUNATA HARGYONO, MUZAYIN NAZARUDDIN, LUTHFI ADAM, SARI DAMAR RATRI, M. FATHI RAYYANI

The Southeast Asian Frontier (SEAF) #1: Highlands took place at the Department of Communication, Universitas Islam Indonesia (UII), Yogyakarta, from 18-20 August 2022. Muzayin Nazaruddin (Department of Communications UII), Luthfi Adam (Research Fellow at the Institute for Advanced Research, Monash Indonesia), Sindhunata Hargyono (Ph.D. Candidate at the Anthropology Department, Northwestern University), Sari Damar Ratri (Ph.D. Candidate at the Anthropology Department, Northwestern University), and M. Fathi Rayyani (Researcher, Research Center for Ecology and Ethnobiology, National Research and Innovation Agency Indonesia) co-convened the workshop. SEAF received financial support from two institutions: (1) Universitas Islam Indonesia via the Global Engagement Grant 2022 and Forum Amir Effendi Siregar Program, and (2) the Regional Science Association International (RSAI) through the Nurturing Young Talent Program 2022. Volunteer coordinators affiliated with the Department of Communications UII also played a crucial role in running the workshop: Zarkoni (publication and administration), Yudi Winarto (consumption and hospitality), Putri Asriyani (Zoom technicality), and Marjito Iskandar Tri Gunawan (documentation).

The workshop, held for three days in a hybrid format, featured 30 selected participants chosen from nearly 60 abstract submissions. These participants represented institutions from 11 different countries, including China, Finland, France, Germany, Indonesia, Malaysia, Sweden, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, the Philippines, and the United States of America. The selection process prioritized Ph.D. students and early career scholars/researchers. The 30 abstracts covered a range of scholarly disciplines: anthropology, archaeology, architecture, biology, communication, forestry, geography, history, literature, philology, and sociology. We organized these presentations into nine panels with eight themes, each receiving constructive feedback from pre-invited discussants: conservation and environmentalism (Faizah Zakaria, Nanyang Technological University), development (Mona Chettri, independent scholar), government (Luthfi Adam, Monash Indonesia), natural hazards and social resilience (Fajar Thufail, National Research and Innovation Agency Indonesia), political economic changes (Micah Fisher, University of Hawaii at Manoa, and Sari Ratri, Northwestern University), religious changes (Imam Ardhianto, Universitas

Indonesia), representation (Muzayin Nazaruddin, Universitas Islam Indonesia), and scientific practices (Anthony Medrano, Yale-NUS College).

Keynote

The workshop featured three keynote speakers who participated online. On the first day, Tania Li (University of Toronto) delivered her keynote speech titled, *Two Capitalism, Two Commodity Frontiers: A View from Indonesia*. We invited Tania due to her extensive and impactful research on Indonesian highland frontiers. In her talk, Tania argued that labelling corporate-occupied commodity frontiers as capitalist, with notions of free market and competition, obscures the fact that corporations behind large-scale concessions often rely on forced land seizures, labour coercion, and state subsidies. Additionally, this narrative normalizes the marginalization of small-scale farmers, who historically have been the most productive and dynamic actors on commodity frontiers, despite lacking the same support and recognition as their corporate counterparts.

On the second day, Michael Eilenberg (Aarhus University) delivered his keynote speech. We invited Michael not only because of his research in the highland borderlands of West Kalimantan, but also his recent co-edited work on the concept of Frontier Assemblage (Cons and Eilenberg 2019). Titled, *Smoke, Fire, and Crisis on the Indonesian Forest Frontier*, Michael's talk began with a comprehensive introduction to the frontier concept, particularly how it is influenced by the Turner Thesis. He then illustrated, in his talk, how the burning of land and forests is part of a broader assemblage of land appropriation that is essential in creating an 'investable' environment for large-scale plantation development.

On the third day, Timo Maran (University of Tartu) proposed a semiotic approach to investigate highlands, highlanders, outsiders, and their dynamic interrelations. In his talk titled, *Towards a Semiotics of Ecocultures: Semiotic Ground and Ecosphere*, Timo argued that semiotically-informed humanities and social sciences studies about highlands will seriously consider human-environment relations, including highlanders-highlands relations, as semiotic relations, not merely physical relations. Timo proposed some semiotic tools to analyse dynamic interrelationships between humans and environments, such as the concept of semiotic ground, eco-cultures, and eco-sphere. He further argued that iconic and indexical signs constitute a common semiotic ground for human and non-human species alike that is also

connected to the patterns of the material realm. In icons and indexes, there exists a connection between object and interpretation and, accordingly, between material and semiotic realms.

Contributions to Southeast Asian Highlands Studies

Core-periphery relations, in their various manifestations, play a prominent role in spatializing socio-political relationships in studies of Southeast Asia's past and present. Departing from the premise that 'expansion' is a significant mode of spatializing power, especially from polities or institutions with a centralising tendency (i.e., the core), we are convinced that the concept of the 'frontier' serves as an appropriate heuristic, if not theory, to understand this predominantly one-sided imposition of relations between the core and periphery. In this workshop, we viewed the frontier as a socio-spatial framework where potentialities and limitations converge from the perspective of the core, often followed by attempts to subjugate marginal locations considered to be the 'frontier'.¹ The inherent ambiguity of the frontier acts as a lure that energizes actors from the core establishment to engage in expansionary activities into the periphery or margin.

We selected 'highland' as the theme for our first workshop due to its pervasive presence in Southeast Asia's geographical landscape. Additionally, core-periphery relations in Southeast Asia often mirror this geography, resulting in the prominence of the core/lowland and periphery/highland dichotomy as a prevalent understanding of how power is spatialized in Southeast Asian historiography and ethnography. However, we also recognize that significant works on Southeast Asian highlands have mainly originated from areas within the Southeast Asian mainland.² Therefore, we intentionally leveraged our engagement with insular Southeast Asian highlands, particularly in Indonesia, in the hope of identifying and amplifying

1. In defining this framework we are inspired by works of Geiger 2008; Li 2014; Tsing 2005; Cons and Eilenberg 2019; Acciaioli and Sabharwal 2017.

2. For instance Leach 2004; Scott 2009; Jonsson 2014

more work from this region and bringing it together with research on highlands in mainland Southeast Asia through the lens of the frontier heuristic.

When we issued the call for papers for this workshop, we anticipated that most submissions would revolve around issues of state formation and capitalist expansion into marginalized highland spaces. Indeed, this was the case: we organized papers on these topics into three panels consisting of four sessions each (Political Economic Change in Highlands I and II, Highlands and Development, and Governing Southeast Asian Highlands). However, we were also pleased to see how participants responded to our call by delving into issues such as religious changes, conservation and environmentalism, and scientific practices in Southeast Asian highlands.

In this first round of SEAF, the selected papers deeply engaged with the forces that shape and reshape the past and present of Southeast Asian highlands, often situating the highlands within the context of larger and/or exogenous forces and actors. However, the degree of engagement with the frontier heuristic differed significantly among the selected papers, with some explicitly utilizing the heuristic to frame their analysis and others not even mentioning the term. Our primary goal as conveners remains the explicit framing of Southeast Asian highland studies using the frontier heuristic. Consequently, we are planning to hold a second workshop focused on the publication, where we will invite selected presenters to refine their papers and effectively employ the frontier heuristic in framing their excellent works on the Southeast Asian highlands.

Additional Highlights

Aditya Kiran Kakati (International Institute for Asian Studies, Leiden University) was awarded the workshop's best paper prize for his work titled, *Inviting and Evading States: A 'Vacuum' in Highland Zomia After Global War (1945) in the Indo-Burmese Border-worlds*. His historically grounded research complicates the narrative of Zomian highlanders 'evading the state' by revealing the oscillation between resisting and inviting states among highlanders residing in former colonial frontiers. Additionally, his work pays serious attention to the fragile temporality of post-war and post-colonial state formation.

Challenges and Shortcomings

From the perspective of the conveners, we acknowledge three notable challenges and shortcomings encountered during the workshop. Firstly, the majority of the papers submitted and selected focused on Indonesian highlands. This issue may be attributed to the amplification of the conveners' network bias. In the future, we are committed to implementing a more comprehensive marketing strategy for our call-for-papers to encourage submissions from studies conducted outside of Indonesia.

Secondly, we experienced a significant technical issue related to Zoom during Tania Li's keynote speech. We express our gratitude to Tania for her commitment to completing her speech despite the interruption caused by an incorrect Zoom account used to host the meeting room. Moving forward, we will ensure greater attention to technical details to minimize such disruptions.

Thirdly, we failed to acknowledge the IMEI registration policy in Indonesia to participants from outside the country using non-Indonesian smartphones. As a result, some participants were unable to access cellular signals despite having an Indonesian SIM card inserted into their devices. In the future, we will be more attentive to this issue and ensure that appropriate measures are taken to address it.

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Review of *Reworking Culture: Relatedness, Rites, and Resources in Garo Hills, North-East India* by Erik de Maaker

ANNA NOTSU

Erik de Maaker. *Reworking Culture: Relatedness, Rites, and Resources in Garo Hills, North East India*. 2022. Oxford and New Delhi. Oxford University Press. 328 pp., £54 (Hardcover)/₹1695 (Hardcover). ISBN: 978-8-1948-3169-3.

Keywords: Highland Northeast India, Niam, Community Religion, Modernity, Garo Hills

Reworking Culture is based on the author's ethnographic engagement with people in and around the village of Sadolpara in the West Garo Hills in highland Northeast India (HNEI), where he conducted more than 20 years of fieldwork. It cunningly deals with the broader anthropological question of what ties people to the place they live in, in an attempt to critically explore the concept of 'cultural identity' from emic perspectives. To de Maaker, the idea of community, much like 'culture', becomes manifest in the sustained enactment of mutual relations that people continuously create, maintain and transform through everyday interactions and in response to material conditions and political and economic opportunities. By carefully examining such nuanced networks of sociality, the author showcases the dynamic of Garo village life.

Central to de Maaker's argument is what constitutes 'a shared livelihood that demands cooperation and sustains a village community' (p. 213). But rather than ascribing primordialist bonds, the author spotlights how the Garos continue to practise

Reworking Culture

Relatedness, Rites, & Resources in Garo Hills, North East India

ERIK DE MAAKER

and take pride in their ‘Garoness’, notwithstanding the form of social change emerging from within (Chapter 1). This is evinced by his portrayal of *niam*, an orally-passed-down set of social principles that uphold ways of behaving towards others, including plants, animals, spirits and deities. How it operates is situational and requires a community consensus on what is (not) appropriate. Fulfilling social expectations and obligations through the interpretation of *niam* becomes indicative of Garo living. In Chapter 2, he elaborates on the point of ‘being Garo’ by explaining a larger political and economic patterning of community-making. Ethnicity, religion and kinship – each of these social dimensions may shape the relationship between Garos, yet, they alone do not fully explain how Garos define themselves and find meaning in their established relationships. *Niam*, de Maaker demonstrates, while prevalently deemed traditional and immutable, is instrumental in foregrounding when and what relational categories become relevant and how they become subject to adaptation, redefinition and contestation across different social domains (Chapter 3).

The relationships that Garos forge with one another are, however, not confined to the realm of ‘people’. Through offerings and celebrations related to the growth of crops, for instance, they acknowledge the value of maintaining good relationships with spirits that are omnipresent in nature. The author points out that both practitioners of the Garo ‘community’ religion (Songsareks) and Christian Garos, despite their different religious positioning, similarly value ceremonial occasions, at which a sense of belonging – religious, genealogical, social – is respectively expressed through the act of sharing drinks and meals. Funerary rituals especially exemplify how people attempt to strategically and symbolically continue such social relations through negotiation. The dead, whether in the form of a physical body, immaterial soul or ghost, demands the living honour the relationship with the deceased and respect the matrilineal structure by finding a replacement for deceased spouses. This allows more flexible interpretations of *niam* for specific social gains and losses that are deemed important. Garos’ ontological understandings of ‘place’ – as agricultural land, a seat of spirits and also a matrilineal unit of property – extend beyond mere physical attributes, as described by the author as “House”. This encompasses intricate entanglements of religious, political and economic responsibilities and commitments to preserving the rights and property to which they belong (Chapters 4, 5 and 6).

In the subsequent chapters, the author explains that *niam*, however traditional it may be, becomes subject to reorientation in response to emergent changes in the ecological conditions essential for Garos’ livelihood. As available resources become increasingly scarce, he points out, the nature of ‘sharing’ in the sense of mutual dependencies also begins to shift in pursuit of securing access to resources, land titles and rights and accumulating privatised wealth, namely, cash. While ordinarily, to Garos, ‘prestige is gained by *giving* rather than *having* (p. 231), the meaning of ownership is redefined through marriage and hierarchical arrangements within inter-House relations. Furthermore, the author elucidates that the growing number of development initiatives in rural Garo Hills, too, brings out new ways of achieving and maintaining the status quo. The relationships that Garos create and maintain with civil servants and government officials depend on their positionality and personal connections. Those Garo, like village heads, who are entitled to have direct access to greater powers can earn prestige through the redistribution of, thus ‘giving’, funds to their kin. In this sense, *niam* is and will be continuously reinterpreted in line with the ecological and political current – insofar as Garos consider it vital to their way of living (Chapters 7 and 8).

The author seeks to bring rural life and traditional practices into focus, not to romanticise nor salvage Garo village life, but to identify within it collective negotiations, reinterpretations and reorientations that constitute ‘Garoness’. To illustrate such complex Garo logics, instead of merely explaining what they are, de Maaker shares with the reader his process of learning about the diversity of relatedness that Garos establish with ‘others’. By illuminating the agency of Garos this way, the author foregrounds emergent issues and concerns shared not only within the Garo Hills but also across HNEI regarding accelerating nature commodification and ‘remote’ identity. The latter is especially questioned in this book, through which to think about how differentiated disparities and inequalities are increasingly overlooked, and sometimes reinforced, in cultural terms.

Reworking Culture is an ethnography with the mission to challenge dominant views on what a 'traditional culture' may entail. But the scope of this book goes well beyond de-essentialisation. At the vanguard of climate change, biodiversity loss and increasing global pressure to 'modernise' the economy, agriculture and education, amid immense transformations, the Garo Hills that de Maaker portrays is also a harbinger of *resistance* to certain changes – not as a relic of the timeless past, but as an important element of Garoness today. The book brings to the fore pliable processes of community-making within an 'indigenous' village context in HNEI whilst highlighting much larger historical contingencies and future implications, relevant to those interested in the intersection of religion and livelihood across and beyond HNEI.

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